

LandSense

A Citizen Observatory and Innovation Marketplace
for Land Use and Land Cover Monitoring

Deliverable 5.7

Good practice guidelines, protocols and benchmarking standards for quality assurance

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Short Description:
The final deliverable (D5.7) from the Quality Assurance (QA) work package of the LandSense project summarises the project’s findings, focusing on general good practice guidance relating to QA service delivery for citizen observatories. The design and implementation of data protocols and key QA services is discussed using experience gained across LandSense’s diverse set of pilot studies and themes. The results of benchmarking Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) data collected by LandSense contributors against national authoritative LULC datasets are described and the potential for citizen-contributed data to reduce the cost of producing LULC datasets in the future are discussed.
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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	11
1 Introduction.....	12
2 Data Protocols	13
2.1 The evolution of the LandSense data models	13
2.2 Good practice guidance for data structure and design	14
3 Good practice guidelines.....	17
3.1 QA processing for polygonal data	17
3.1.1 Overlap detection	18
3.1.2 Overlap correction.....	19
3.2 Photo quality checks.....	20
3.2.1 Blur check	20
3.2.2 Illumination check	22
3.2.3 Image size and resolution.....	26
3.3 Privacy checks on photo data	26
3.3.1 Face detection service (FDS)	31
3.3.2 License plate detection	32
3.3.3 A revised good practice workflow for privacy checks on photographs	36
3.4 QA checks for positional accuracy and offset.....	37
3.5 QA checks for contributor agreement.....	39
3.6 QA checks for categorical accuracy	41
4 Benchmarking.....	45
4.1 Benchmark method	45
4.1.1 Legend harmonization.....	46
4.2 OSMLanduse.org	52
4.3 Case studies	53
4.3.1 Case study: Germany (Heidelberg).....	54
4.3.1.1 Digitales Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS) DE – data description.....	54
4.3.1.2 ATKIS and OSMLanduse Comparison.....	54
4.3.1.3 CORINE Land Cover (CLC) and OSMLanduse Comparison	56
4.3.2 Case study: France (Toulouse).....	58
4.3.2.1 OCS-GE data description	58

4.3.2.2 OCS-GE and OSMLanduse Comparison.....	59
4.3.2.3 CORINE Land Cover (CLC) and OSMLanduse Comparison	62
4.3.3 Case study: Austria (Vienna).....	64
4.3.3.1 Realnutzung – data description	64
4.3.3.2 Realnutzung and OSMLanduse Comparison.....	65
4.3.3.3 CORINE Land Cover and OSMLanduse Comparison	67
4.4 Citizen-contributed data and cost reductions.....	68
5 Conclusions.....	70
References.....	73

List of Figures

Figure 1: Distribution of blur level results for LandSense imagery. Red bars represent images with significant blurring, orange bars represent images with slight blurring and the blue bar shows images without blurring	21
Figure 2: Example of image sharpening results: Original image on left and sharpened image on the right (from the Paysages pilot)	22
Figure 3: Example of very poor quality image (left) and the failed attempt to correct for darkness and blurriness (right).....	22
Figure 4: Brightness level spectrum for images below the predefined brightness threshold. Brightness levels of images shown (from left to right) are 0,2,8,36,46,56,68,81 and 94.....	23
Figure 5: Image brightness level spectrum for images classified as bright. Brightness levels of images shown (from left to right) are 110, 139, 151, 171, 185 and 217	23
Figure 6: Distribution of image brightness results for all LandSense pilot images processed by the QA service. Red bars indicate brightness levels outside acceptable levels. Yellow bars indicate brightness levels of indeterminate quality. Blue bars represent where overall image brightness is at an acceptable level	24
Figure 7: Example of improving image brightness. Original image on left. Corrected image (right) has brightness level increased by 40% and contrast reduced by 20%	25
Figure 8: example of image brightening and the effect on the FDS accuracy. [Left] Original image (with actual face obscured by yellow star to preserve privacy) – no faces detected. [Centre] Image with brightness increased by 40%. [Right] Output of FDS on brightened image with green boxes highlighting successful face detection	25
Figure 9: Example of the effect of image resolution on face detection accuracy. [Left] original image processed through the FDS showing two potential faces (highlighted in green). [Right] Results from the FDS of processing Image up scaled to 300dpi showing four potential faces.....	26
Figure 10: Examples of images where face is present in image but not clearly visible. Classed as a failure but it is arguable as to whether the people in these images are actually recognisable	28
Figure 11: Example of image where license plates are present but not detected although angle and distance of license plates to the camera makes it ambiguous as to whether the license plate is clearly visible and recognisable	28
Figure 12: Examples of commission errors. [Left] face detection service incorrectly detected four faces in this image when only one (figure on right) is actually visible. The other three figures are facing away from the camera, with only the back of their heads visible [Right] License plate detection service incorrectly identifies and blurs portion of signage on a container as a license plate.....	28
Figure 13: City.Oases App screenshots illustrating options for manual blurring of privacy features	30

Figure 14: City.Oases images where commercially licensed license plate detection service performed better than LandSense version (detected licence plates highlighted in purple)	33
Figure 15: Examples of images with vehicle license plates present and not detected by LandSense or commercial versions of OpenALPR	34
Figure 16: Image from the Paysages pilot showing performance differences between the two commercial LPDS tested. In both images, the license plates have been obscured to maintain privacy. [Left] Results from commercial version of OpenALPR with detected license plate highlighted in pink, [Right] Results from PlateRecogniser LPDS showing additional license plate detected highlighted in blue	34
Figure 17: Images where PlateRecogniser detected license plates not identified by the LandSense LPDS or the commercial version of OpenALPR. Note the presence of a commission error related to the construction signage on the right hand side of the image on the left. License plates detected are highlighted in blue with the actual license plates obscured to maintain privacy	34
Figure 18: Zoomed in image of license plate ‘failures’ shown in Figure 15 [left]	35
Figure 19: Zoomed in image of license plate ‘failures’ shown in Figure 15 [right]	36
Figure 21: Location and boundaries of the pilot cities involved: Heidelberg (HEI), Toulouse (TLS) and Vienna (VIE)	45
Figure 22: Heidelberg comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and ATKIS 2018. The top row shows the original products and the bottom row shows the difference where grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the ATKIS difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for agricultural land (yellow) and forests (green)	55
Figure 23: Heidelberg comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC2018. Top row shows original products, the bottom row shows differences while the grey area shows agreement. The largest mismatches are shown in yellow (arable land) for the CLC data and white (agricultural areas) for similar areas of the OSMLanduse data	57
Figure 24. Toulouse comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and OCS-GE land cover 2016. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the OCS-GE difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for urban fabric (red) and forests (green)	60
Figure 25. Toulouse comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC2018. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the CLC difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes with industrial/commercial (pink) and arable land (yellow) also present. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for urban fabric (red) and forests (green).....	63

Figure 26. Vienna comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and Realnutzung. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas show agreement. The Realnutzung difference map indicates that the majority of the mismatches relate to industrial/commercial (pink), urban fabric (red), arable land (yellow) and forest (green) land classes. The OSMLanduse difference map shows similar class differences except that forests and arable land are replaced by agricultural areas (white) 65

Figure 27. Vienna comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas indicate agreement. The CLC difference map [bottom left] shows a diverse set of mismatched LULC classes as does the difference map for OSMLanduse [bottom right]. Urban fabric (red) is mismatched with Industrial/Commercial (pink) and forests (green) and arable land (yellow) are mismatched with the more general agricultural areas (white) in the LULC classification. . 67

List of Tables

Table 1: The set of LandSense data quality analyses applied to different LandSense pilots. The numbers in each cell indicate the number of checks carried out for that QA service and pilot. Grey cells indicate that that particular QA service was not applicable for the given pilot study. [Source D5.6 - Quality evaluation of citizen-observed data to the LandSense pilot studies II]	17
Table 2: List of datasets that were benchmarked against the citizen science sourced OSMLanduse LULC mapping data. There were six maps (one NMA and one CLC for each of the three case studies) with two comparisons made for the OCS-GE (Toulouse) map (one for LU data values and one for LC data values) making a total of seven benchmarking comparisons against the OSMLanduse data.....	46
Table 3: Legend harmonization of CLC-based OSMLanduse legend towards digitale Landschaftskarte of Amtliches Topographisch-Kartographisches Informationssystem (ATKIS) 2018 (DE) for Heidelberg; OCS-GEO 2016 (FR) for Toulouse; Realnutzung 2018 (AU) for Vienna; CLC Legend 2018; * class 3.0 was used for Heidelberg exclusively towards the ATKIS comparison	48
Table 4. Nomenclature of OSMLanduse.org and the tag-based legend harmonization towards CLC, modified (merged class 2.4 into 2.1, class 3.0 into class 3.1 and classes 4.1, 4.2 into 5.0) from Schultz et al. (2017) ..	52
Table 5: Heidelberg confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show ATKIS (Overall agreement – 57.7%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement	56
Table 6: Heidelberg confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show CLC 2018 (overall agreement is 58.6%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement	58
Table 7. Toulouse confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show OCS-GE LC classes 2016 (overall agreement = 36.1%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement	61
Table 8. Toulouse confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show OCS-GE LU classes 2016 (Overall agreement = 44.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement	62
Table 9. Toulouse confusion matrix - rows show area percentages OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show CLC2018 (overall agreement = 46.5%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement.....	64
Table 10. Vienna confusion matrix -rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018, columns show Realnutzung (overall agreement = 49.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement	66
Table 11. Vienna confusion matrix - rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 area and columns show CLC (overall agreement = 31.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement.....	68
Table 12: Good practice summary table	71

Executive Summary

Citizen observatories offer a potential advancement in the field of Land Use and Land Cover (LULC) monitoring, greatly increasing the capacity and frequency of data collection, enabling, for example, near-real-time response to emerging environmental hazards (e.g., deforestation, flooding). However, concerns have been raised about the quality of volunteered geographic information (VGI) when compared to the traditional land surveying techniques and methods employed by national mapping agencies. A key element of the LandSense citizen observatory, described in this report, was to provide robust quality assurance tools and methods to ensure that the quality of VGI data can be characterised and made effective for user needs.

This final deliverable (D5.7) from the Quality Assurance (QA) work package of the LandSense project builds upon the findings to-date and focuses on general good practice guidance for data protocols and QA services. It also includes the results of benchmarking LULC data collected by LandSense contributors against national authoritative LULC datasets.

The design of data models and protocols for their use in citizen observatories are discussed, emphasising the need to balance consistency and flexibility across a diverse set of pilot studies. Evolution of data design models varied greatly across the pilot studies, and it is evident that QA services should be designed to allow for changes to the underlying data model while minimising disruption to the design of the QA services. The four key concepts to be considered in forming a robust data model from a QA perspective (Adaptability, Version control, Accessibility and Data Protection) are described.

To evaluate the potential value and accuracy of crowdsourced LULC data, the OSMLanduse¹ product was compared with authoritative mapping datasets for three EU countries included in the LandSense pilot studies (Germany, France and Austria). The results of this benchmarking exercise showed strong agreement in the majority of land use categories when compared to the EU CORINE Land Cover (CLC) classification system. Agreement was less strong when compared to National Mapping Agency (NMA) products. Distinguishing between different types of built up areas (e.g., between urban fabric and commercial/industrial land use) and specific agricultural land uses were found to be areas where differences were most commonly identified across all three countries.

Good practice guidelines for each of the high-level QA services developed as part of the LandSense project form the heart of this report. These include checks on polygonal data, image quality and privacy checks, positional accuracy and offset, contributor agreement and categorical accuracy. For each service, QA issues relating to its implementation are described, such as: how success/failure may be defined, dealing with borderline cases, examples of both good and poor practice and potential methods identified for improvement.

¹ <https://osmlanduse.org/>

1 Introduction

Citizen science for the provision of geographical data has a long history and is known by a variety of terms (See et al., 2016) but has developed rapidly since the advent of volunteered geography and volunteered geographical information (VGI) pioneered by Goodchild (2007). The term VGI is taken here to relate to information provided by the public for little if any reward. Developments such as Web 2.0 and the proliferation of inexpensive location aware devices has greatly eased the acquisition of VGI and resulted in a considerable growth in the subject.

In the context of the LandSense project, the information provided by citizens relates primarily to land use and land cover (LULC). The vast potential of VGI to replace or augment authoritative geographical data on LULC, which can be expensive to acquire or have restrictions on access and use, has been widely recognised (Fonte et al., 2015b; Stehman et al., 2018). Indeed, citizens can be a highly attractive source of data on LULC, addressing concerns such as the amount, spatial distribution and timeliness of authoritative data. However, there are many concerns about the quality of citizen-derived data such as its trustworthiness, distribution and heterogeneity (Fonte et al., 2015a). As such, quality assessment has been a major issue in citizen science projects such as LandSense.

There are many dimensions to data quality (Fonte et al., 2015b) but the concern in this document is focused entirely on the data acquired for the LandSense project and its objectives. Early work, reported in Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1), focused on the various means to explore the quality of citizen-contributed data that formed the basis of the LandSense quality assurance tools. The approaches reported in the literature, and notably in the work of COST Action TD1202 (Foody et al., 2017) and the COBWEB project (Higgins et al., 2016), which underpinned the development of LandSense, were assessed for possible use. As reported in other deliverables, a set of quality assurance tools to meet the objectives of the LandSense project were developed and tested (see, for example, D5.4 and D5.6). In the course of this activity, good practices for quality assurance of citizen-contributed data emerged. These are reported here. Although the discussion is focused on only LandSense applications, much of the material should have broader relevance and could be applicable or adaptable to other studies. In addition, while one concern with data arising from citizens, rather than authoritative, sources is that data acquisition is typically undertaken without adherence to strict protocols and working to defined standards. The focus here is on good and not best practices; there is no desire to alienate the citizen community by making the acquisition process onerous or difficult (Foody et al. 2017).

Chapter 2 focuses on data, looking at data collection protocols and how these have evolved over time. It also describes findings and guidance for data structure and design that arose from the work. The focus of this report, i.e., good practice guidance, can be found in chapter 3. Guidelines are provided for each of the QA tools developed and implemented during the LandSense project. Chapter 4 considers benchmarking and focuses on two of the pilot studies, comparing VGI data on LULC, collected by the OpenStreetMap land use mapping application (OSMLanduse.org), against authoritative LULC datasets from National Mapping Agencies (NMAs) for the same locations and time periods. Conclusions, including a summary table of good practices for each QA service, are provided in chapter 5.

2 Data Protocols

Protocols are methods for the effective acquisition and combination of data from various sources and using different techniques. Within this project, this covers generic data standards, conflation procedures and methods for quality estimation that enable data to be compared against other products and results. An example of the latter would be the use of error matrices to describe the quality of data products, as outlined in the benchmarking chapter of this report (see chapter 4).

Data standards for LandSense, and how these interact with QA procedures, were initially outlined in deliverable D5.2 (Schultz, 2018). This introduced the concept of essential and recommended Data Collection Requirements (eDCRs and rDCRs, respectively). DCRs define the nature of the data collected and how it relates to the QA functions. eDCRs relate to mandatory data requirements, such as privacy checks on photographic data (referred to as ‘photos’ from this point onwards for brevity), observations and time stamps on observations. rDCRs are not mandatory requirements but relate to data protocols aimed at promoting good data quality. These include checking photos for blurring and poor illumination levels, thresholds for positional accuracy of observations and rules on validity of the sampling population for observations. Research undertaken in the LandSense project, including common data collection standards such as DCRs, along with common data protocols, can support future research in citizen observatories.

This chapter provides a briefing of LandSense pilots and their data protocols, and then describes good practices relating to data structure and design for citizen observatories, based on the LandSense experience and from a QA perspective.

2.1 The evolution of the LandSense data models

LandSense pilot studies and their apps were developed using a variety of scripting languages, different version control systems and different deployment platforms. The federated approach tried to accommodate for these differences in terms of accessibility and use. Their common characteristics are:

- i. Shared accessibility platform and connection mechanism through the LandSense Engagement Platform (LEP)
- ii. The use of a federated login system, the LandSense federation, to allow users to use a single authentication system to access and use LandSense applications and data across multiple themes and pilot studies
- iii. The use of a common quality control entity to identify, assess and potentially correct data quality concerns across these multiple applications, themes and pilot studies.

Throughout the evolution of LandSense, all pilot studies were open to change and adaptation throughout their development regarding their concept, audience, content, and technicalities. This enabled them to focus better on user needs and to take lessons learnt during initial data collection campaigns in 2018 into account. As a result, data protocols evolved and were subjected to reconsideration and reframing. Hence, a key aspect for good practice of the LandSense data protocols is the ability to accommodate these dynamics. A central

feature of LandSense data protocols was to ensure that ongoing operational use and development could occur simultaneously.

The lack of centralized oversight for the different pilot studies enabled individual development of the pilots but eroded the use of common data protocols. As a result, the LandSense pilot apps behaved differently in terms of their development strategies, format and their evolution over time.

The most notable evolutions occurred for the pilots of the urban landscape dynamics theme. For example, *Frei.Raum.Netz* Vienna rebranded to *City.Oases* and changed its data collection protocol and data schema to take better account of user needs. The *Paysages* pilot also evolved between the two campaigns in 2018 and 2019 by focusing on more citizen-friendly tasks such as validation and LULC classification to take the lessons learned from initial data collection campaigns into account. This resulted in the simplification of the data collection protocol and data model. The *OpenStreetMap* land use application (*OSMLanduse*) evolved, with its validation methods becoming more robust during the pilot study. Different modes for the collection of land use reference data were introduced, most notably by estimation of contributor agreement. The final urban pilot study, *MijnPark.NL*, started in the second year of LandSense and was built upon insights gained up to this point, particularly within *City.Oases*. The initial data protocols and routines were not subjected to any significant modification and proved both stable and fit-for-purpose. The *MijnPark.NL* pilot may, therefore, serve as a role model for the design and deployment of a citizen science project dealing with citizen perception. In contrast, the pilots of the agricultural (*CropSupport*) and forest monitoring (*Natura.Alert*) themes evolved more gradually until they eventually reached maturity without any fundamental changes within their foci, content, or data schema.

Balancing the need for each pilot study to develop its own bespoke data model whilst maintaining some standardization of the data models across the LandSense project was an ongoing challenge throughout the project. This is not surprising given the diversity of the pilot studies. In addition, the differing requirements of the various stakeholders to the LandSense project (e.g., users, government, commercial and academic) also had to be considered and impacted on the development of the data model. For example, commercial partners may be reluctant to release their Intellectual Property (IP) under open access conditions whereas funding organisations (e.g., the EU, national funding bodies, etc.) may require open access as part of the funding conditions. Some of the key lessons learnt and good practices identified from building a data model given these conflicting inputs and audiences are provided in the following section.

2.2 Good practice guidance for data structure and design

Data structure is the term used to describe a collection of data values, the relationships between these values and the functions and operations that can be applied to that set of values. In this context, design refers to how this data structure was developed. Cohesion, adaptability, and accessibility are the three concepts that govern successful design of data structures for the LandSense pilot studies. The design of LandSense specific data structures was characterized by an initial design phase, as described in D5.2 (Schultz, 2018), followed by concurrent developmental and operational use. Changes and adaptations to the pilot studies, either

motivated by changing user demands or foci readjustments, were the norm. The need to offer scientific insights, results and commercial exploitation were constant demands.

Within this section, we provide the experiences gathered and identify uniform principles that citizen science data structures and data design should support for broad use within LandSense-like frameworks or citizen observatories. The principles identified are largely manifest conceptually although in some instances, they can be linked to distinct technical processes. They are defined as follows:

- I) Cohesion: the capacity to use the pilot studies in a combined manner such that they shall benefit one another and may reuse parts where appropriate. Cohesion can be aided by agreeing on shared standards and allocating attention where objectively needed. An integral part of successful cohesion is the documentation of the evolution of the pilot studies. This can support reasoned decision making about the potential convergence, or divergence, of a pilot study's data structure from previous experiences. For example, as stated in section 2.1, the development and stability of the MijnPark.NL data structure was aided by prior development of the City.Oases data structure. Specific aspects of cohesion include:
 - a) Uniform usage of established geo-data standards: To simplify access and reduce friction for data access, particularly with an interlinked federation environment such as that provided by LandSense, and to accommodate for near-real-time quality checks, we suggest : a) to use *.geojson standard for vector data. The format is robust, potentially human readable, adaptable, and suited for web applications and b) to use the Geodetic coordinate system for the World (EPSG:4326), which is the default projection of *.geojson. A global projection supports deployment scalability and is particularly important for integrating data collection across the world (such as Natura.Alert).
 - b) Coding language: For research and data analysis we recommend R because of its availability and flexibility, for instance, to adapt quality checks or data analysis rapidly. For operational implementation, we recommend Python due to its high performance; most LandSense pilots and routine functionalities such as artificial intelligence (AI) devices are written in Python or can be modified within Python. Both R and Python can be installed at no cost, are human readable and understandable by a broader academic and non-academic public.
 - c) Versioning and control: Code developments should be maintained within a git (gitLab, gitHub) environment allowing multiple developers to link and follow changes to the code repository. The git shall be managed and moderated by the project coordinator. We also suggest that storing code on local machines should be avoided. Code available on a git does have the chance to be used for adaptation or further development.
- II) Adaptability: The capacity to keep a citizen science project flexible in terms of the requirements dictated by commercial, technical, scientific or policy constraints.
 - a) Technical adaptability: Either the technology or the focus of the pilot might change rapidly either by the availability of novel technologies or by a change in the pilot intentions, aims or desired target groups. Hence, the choice of a suitable data structure and design must support rapid adaptability of the technical setup.

- b) **Deployment scalability for effective use:** Once a citizen science app is picked up by the public or a certain audience, the app data protocol must support a rapid up-scale or downscaling capacity depending on the intensity of use. We recommend containerized deployment chunks through Docker containers (Merkel, 2014) and eventually Docker swarms (Freeman, 2017) or similar, which can be extended as needed and can be deployed within cloud platforms and as such adapt elastically to increased usage intensity.
 - c) A key element of friction in deeply interlinked and integrated processes is alteration of data schemas, particularly adding entirely new features. Hence the pilot must support a dynamic inflation of placeholders for feature collection or processing.
- III) **Accessibility:** coordinated management of access for functions provided on the git repositories and exposure of those functionalities for a broader audience where appropriate, including inclusive deployment of the science effort.
- a) **Privacy:** ensure the privacy of the contributor from the very first data entry. Contributors opting out of the pilot shall have the possibility to take their data records with them. This is an important part of the broader issue of ensuring GDPR compliance. However, in some instances, privacy may be waived by contributors giving free, informed and willing consent for their contributions to be linked to their identity. The key issue, for EU-based work, is to ensure that GDPR rules are followed when dealing with privacy considerations for data.
 - b) **Openness:** A key aspect of accessibility is the degree to which both data and any associated code and/or applications is openly available for access by both contributors and wider public access. However, complete openness may not always be possible, and when providing open access to data, privacy considerations are of particularly critical importance. Open availability of code developed may sometimes be difficult due to licensing issues. However, good practice should be to reduce such complications wherever possible by avoiding the use of licensed code and/or data.

This section has focused on mainly conceptual issues of good practice and how they relate to the collection, processing and use of data in a citizen observatory-based project. Specific, more concrete, issues relating to good practices for the types of QA services used in such a project can be found in the next section.

3 Good practice guidelines

This chapter focuses on each of the major QA services developed for LandSense. In each case, discussion of the techniques and methods utilised by LandSense are explored, highlighting elements of good practice, areas where improvements could be made, and lessons learnt for future work. Table 1, taken from D5.6 (Long et al., 2020), shows the various LandSense QA checks undertaken, indicating their applicability and the number of checks performed across the various LandSense themes and pilot studies.

Table 1: The set of LandSense data quality analyses applied to different LandSense pilots. The numbers in each cell indicate the number of checks carried out for that QA service and pilot. Grey cells indicate that that particular QA service was not applicable for the given pilot study. [Source D5.6 - Quality evaluation of citizen-observed data to the LandSense pilot studies II]

Theme	Urban landscape dynamics				Agricultural land use	Forest and habitat monitoring
	OSMLanduse validation (UHEI, CHEI)	City.Oases (UBA)	MijnPark.NL (VU)	Paysages (IGN)		
Pilots (institutions)					CropSupport (INOSENS)	Natura.Alert (BLI)
Polygon topology check	-	-		-	202	-
Photo privacy check	-	195	372	260	210	512
Photo illumination check / photo blur check	-	195	372	260	210	512
Positional accuracy	-	878	377	-	207	-
Positional offset	-	443	361	-	211	-
Categorical accuracy	10806	-	-	467	-	571
Contributor agreement	150 sites/points	-	30 sites/points	650 sites/points	-	-

3.1 QA processing for polygonal data

QA checks applicable to polygonal data were developed from the Citizen Observatory WEB (COBWEB) platform, as described in deliverable D5.3 (Meek et al., 2019). The QA checks implemented in the LandSense QA platform related to the detection of overlapping and sliver polygons.

Initially, only two of the pilots included the collection of polygonal data in their apps: CropSupport and Paysages. During development of the Paysages app, it was determined that users should not be able to define or edit polygon data, leaving CropSupport as the only LandSense pilot requiring checks on polygonal data. The nature of the data collected by the CropSupport pilot meant that it only required QA checks for polygon

overlaps. Hence, this section focuses on good practices related to overlapping polygon detection and correction.

3.1.1 Overlap detection

Checking for overlapping polygons is a simple spatial problem, based on standard GIS intersect functions (Burrough et al., 2015) as described in D5.2 (Schultz, 2018). It was originally intended that the polygon overlap functionality would run in near-real-time with the original citizen contribution. Polygons added by users would be checked against existing data and any overlaps would result in the new polygon being rejected. The user would then be asked to redraw the crop boundary polygon. However, in practice, this workflow was not adopted for a variety of reasons including time constraints and functional issues with the originally planned workflow.

The original workflow would have meant that any new polygons added to the CropSupport dataset would be rejected if any overlap with previous polygons was detected. However, there was no method for correcting the original polygon if that was the actual source of error. Another potential problem would occur if a user wished to enrich the polygon data by adding crop boundaries within a larger existing boundary, for example, identifying separate plots of individual crops within a larger field boundary. These limitations, plus difficulties in implementing the QA functionality within the CropSupport app within the time schedules needed for pilot data collection, led to changing the workflow from *near-real-time* to *post-processing*.

The shift to post-processing of the polygonal data for quality removed the functionality issues described above, but it also streamlines the submission process for users, thereby hopefully reducing frustration and increasing engagement for citizens (Foody et al., 2017). However, a post-processing QA model introduces new issues and overheads. In a post-processing approach, the responsibility for correcting polygon overlap errors passes to the data manager for the pilot. This process may be difficult without local knowledge or accurate remotely sensed imagery of the area of the observations from the time they were collected. It also adds additional manual QA processes into the workflow.

Both near-real-time and post-processing of polygon overlaps offers benefits and comes with associated limitations. Alternatively, a hybrid approach may prove to be the most effective solution. For example, the user uploads a new polygon that is checked in real-time and is flagged as overlapping an existing polygon. This is fed back to the user and they can decide whether to redraw their polygon or to add a comment that can be used to assist the campaign manager in the post-processing correction of polygon overlaps.

Another issue to consider relates to the methods used to determine the number of overlapping polygons in a dataset. The LandSense QA service counts each instance of overlap individually (e.g., if two polygons are overlapping, this counts as two overlapping polygons). However, other GIS tools, for example QGIS's topology checker², would count the same example as a single instance of overlapping. The difference between the number of overlaps and the number of overlapping polygons can lead to confusion when comparing results

² http://docs.qgis.org/2.18/en/docs/user_manual/plugins/plugins_topology_checker.html

from different tools. Good practice requires that documentation is, therefore, clear and transparent to ensure that the meaning is apparent.

3.1.2 Overlap correction

The LandSense QA platform focused on detecting overlapping polygons. The functionality to amend overlapping polygons automatically was not implemented within LandSense as the CropSupport pilot did not request or require this level of functionality. However, options for amending overlaps will be briefly discussed in this section as part of the overall aim of identifying good practice for QA services when working with VGI.

Establishing good practice guidelines requires consideration of the various options within the context of the specific citizen science project being undertaken. For example, the CropSupport pilot focuses on adding polygons representing crop boundaries. Therefore, polygons do not need to be contiguous, but they should not overlap. Conversely, a project using VGI to map land use polygons would need to ensure that polygons are contiguous in addition to not overlapping. Other LULC models might not allow polygons to overlap but could allow a polygon to be within another polygon to enable hierarchical structuring of LULC categories (e.g., sub-categories contained within a higher-level land use category). In each case, the process of identifying overlaps does not alter but the guidelines for dealing with any overlaps identified may vary according to the specific use case.

Options for correcting overlaps between polygons include:

1. **Do not allow overlapping polygons** – This is the default option, used by CropSupport, where users would be required to redraw their polygon if it overlaps an existing polygon. As already discussed, this approach has limitations, in particular, that it assumes the original polygon is correct.
2. **Redraw polygons option** – An extension of option (1), in this case when overlaps are identified, the user is asked whether they wish to redraw their polygon or the boundaries of the existing polygon it overlaps. A potential problem with this option is that it allows a contributor to edit another user's data. There would be no way to guarantee that any edits made to polygons were correct and the original contributor's data could be lost.
3. **Inclusion of polygon editing tools** – Another option, to both help reduce the likelihood of overlaps and to make it easier for users to modify polygons during data collection, would be to include snapping tools into the applications to help users edit polygons (similar to those found in GIS packages).
4. **Flag overlaps and review** - A fourth option would be to ask the user if they wish to redraw their polygon, and if not, to flag both overlapping polygons for review. Users could also be asked to add comments on the overlap that could assist in solving the problem (e.g., users could add a comment stating that the new polygon supersedes the existing data or that the existing polygon needs to be moved so that its boundary touches the new polygon). The overlapping polygons could then be reviewed by the original contributors, or other users, and a consensus could be reached as to the

correct polygon boundaries. This option would require that the tools available to users would include snapping and topological functionalities.

5. **Automatic polygon correction** – Algorithms can be developed using GIS to identify overlaps and potentially remove these errors through the clipping of overlapping polygons (Wadembere and Ogao, 2010). PostGIS (an open source object-based database with extended spatial functionality)³ also has functions to allow polygon topology correction that could be implemented to correct overlaps (Obe and Hsu, 2011). However, caution should be taken when employing automated solutions, as these will simply redraw the polygon boundaries to remove any intersecting areas between them. There would be no way to ensure that the new polygons are an accurate reflection of the crop field boundaries.

3.2 Photo quality checks

Quality metrics for photos can take a number of forms (Ke et al, 2006). For the purposes of LandSense, image brightness and blurriness were the metrics considered to be of interest. Other similar metrics such as image resolution, bit or colour depth and contrast (Szeliski, 2010) could be easily added to the QA platform if required or requested. Less easily quantifiable metrics, such as image orientation (Shima et al, 2017), may require more planning as to their implementation. However, as this type of metric was not a requirement for LandSense, it will not be further discussed.

General good practice would require there to be a predefined threshold value (or values) against which the check is performed. If the result falls outside the set of acceptable values for that image parameter, then the check should return a failure result. Setting an appropriate threshold value for a given photo quality check is further discussed under the subsections for each quality check.

In addition to recording the pass/failure state, it was found that the quantifiable result from the quality check (e.g., brightness level, image resolution, blur level) should be recorded. Retaining the result enables users of the QA system to rerun the quality checks as a post process, with a range of differing thresholds to examine the impacts of variations in the quality procedures.

3.2.1 Blur check

The LandSense QA platform implementation of blur checking calculates an image's blurriness on an eight-bit radiometric scale producing a result in the 0-255 range (where zero is fully blurred and 255 is no blur present). Blur check response results for the LandSense imagery processed were less widely distributed than for other metrics such as brightness (see Figure 6). Less than 3% of the circa 1500 images processed by the LandSense QA service (Table 1) had blur levels below the maximum value of 254. The heavily skewed distribution of blur level values can be seen in Figure 1. Effectively, any image with a blur level below 250 shows blurring of detail and values below 220 are significantly blurred (see section 4.3.1 of D5.6 (Long et al., 2020) for a more detailed

³ See <https://postgis.net/> for a more detailed explanation of the PostGIS database format and its functionality

explanation of this, including examples of image blurring). The nature of this skewed distribution led to the definition of the blur threshold at the 250 level.

Figure 1: Distribution of blur level results for LandSense imagery. Red bars represent images with significant blurring, orange bars represent images with slight blurring and the blue bar shows images without blurring

The usability of a photo is, in part, a function of the blur checking. Therefore, a blurred photo is perfectly fine if estimating something very general and easy to identify such as building height via number of floors, but it is less useful if identifying something very detailed and specific such as crop types. The degree of blurring will also play a part in determining usability.

In addition to identifying good practice for ascertaining whether an image is blurred, it is also important to consider what options are available once a blurred image has been detected. For the purposes of LandSense, and given the low number of blurred images that were found, it was determined either to exclude blurred images from the pilot study datasets or to include them with metadata highlighting their quality issues. Another option that could be considered is to apply a sharpening algorithm to reduce the blurriness of an image. To illustrate the potential of this approach, examples of blurred images were automatically sharpened (as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3). As shown, minor levels of blurring can be fixed using standard sharpening functions in image processing software⁴ (Figure 2) but significant blurring, especially when combined with an already dark image, is not easy to correct (Figure 3).

⁴ The example shown was sharpened using Microsoft Powerpoint's image correction tools, but similar results would be obtained using other image processing software

Figure 2: Example of image sharpening results: Original image on left and sharpened image on the right (from the Paysages pilot)

Figure 3: Example of very poor quality image (left) and the failed attempt to correct for darkness and blurriness (right)

3.2.2 Illumination check

Defining an appropriate threshold for brightness is a major component in determining good practice for illumination checks. As with blurriness checking, the LandSense Illumination check calculates brightness on an eight bit radiometric scale producing a brightness level of 0-255 (where 0 is completely black and 255 is completely white) The brightness level threshold of 100 used in LandSense was defined during the development and testing of the QA platform. The choice of an appropriate threshold is highly dependent on the data collection context and the specific image quality requirements of the project. For example, in terms of context, if images are likely to be taken in poorly lit environments (e.g., at night or indoors), then it may be wise to lower the quality threshold for brightness to increase the likelihood of image submissions passing

the check. Conversely, if the project requirements specify that only high-quality image submissions are acceptable, then the threshold may need to be increased.

Figure 4 illustrates the quality of images that fail to reach the threshold of 100 used by LandSense. It is evident that images at the lower end of the spectrum convey little visual information. However, the images to the right could be deemed of acceptable quality if the aim is to maximise the number of images collected.

Figure 4: Brightness level spectrum for images below the predefined brightness threshold. Brightness levels of images shown (from left to right) are 0,2,8,36,46,56,68,81 and 94

Unlike the blur check function, where extreme image sharpness does not cause quality concerns, there is potential for reduced quality at the other end of the brightness scale. Extremely high levels of brightness can lead to images where detail is lost, as discussed in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020). To illustrate this point, Figure 5 provides a spectrum of LandSense images that passed the brightness check. The majority of these images are of good quality, but it is evident that the two brightest images on the right of the figure show a lowered level of quality. This finding leads to the conclusion that for good practice, it may be best to have both a minimum and maximum threshold value set for illumination checks in future work. It is likely that the maximum brightness threshold would be set relatively higher within the overall brightness scale than the minimum threshold. To illustrate this, the distribution of brightness levels from all the LandSense pilot images processed by the QA service (as shown in Table 1) is shown in Figure 6. The areas of the histogram shown in orange, representing brightness levels below 80 and above 200, indicate images where brightness levels are of poor quality. Yellow bins represent images where quality may be sufficient and highlight where the likely choice of min/max brightness thresholds should be set.

Figure 5: Image brightness level spectrum for images classified as bright. Brightness levels of images shown (from left to right) are 110, 139, 151, 171, 185 and 217

Figure 6: Distribution of image brightness results for all LandSense pilot images processed by the QA service. Red bars indicate brightness levels outside acceptable levels. Yellow bars indicate brightness levels of indeterminate quality. Blue bars represent where overall image brightness is at an acceptable level

If a maximum brightness threshold value of 200 had been implemented within the LandSense QA platform, only three additional images (out of the ~1500 processed) would have failed the illumination check. Two of the three images are completely white and show no detail. The remaining image is the one shown on the far right of Figure 5, which was already identified as low quality.

An important question, as with other quality checks, is what should be done with images that fail to pass the illumination check. Such images could be excluded, marked as being of lower quality or automatically brightened. The latter option may seem an obvious choice, but care should be taken when modifying images collected by users. Depending on the nature of the Intellectual Property (IP) rights for a VGI campaign, it may not be possible to make modifications to user collected images without infringing their rights. It may also be ethically questionable to make changes to data collected by users. If the need to modify user-collected imagery to improve quality is a desired goal of a citizen science campaign, permission for image modification should be included in the data collection agreement with users as part of good practice.

Even where permission is given to modify user-collected data, automatic brightening of images can lead to unforeseen quality issues. To illustrate this, Figure 7 shows the results of brightening an image. The foreground of the brightened image on the right is clearly more distinct than the original image (shown on the left), but brightening has led to other elements of the image, such as the sky and gateposts, losing detail due to over saturation. Depending on the specific element of a photo that is important to the observation, automatic brightening of the entire image could lead to a poorer quality image than the original. It is important that adjustment of photo properties be undertaken in a way that is tailored to the specific needs of a study.

Figure 7: Example of improving image brightness. Original image on left. Corrected image (right) has brightness level increased by 40% and contrast reduced by 20%

Even if automatically brightening an image that failed the illumination check is not used to post-process the images collected, it may still be useful in improving the accuracy of privacy checks. In D5.6 (Long et al., 2020), it was hypothesised that darker images were more likely to generate errors in privacy checks as the privacy features were less clearly identifiable. This hypothesis has been tested and shown to be valid in some cases as shown in Figure 8. The original image (shown on the left) is quite dark and the face of the person in the image was not detected by the LandSense Face Detection Service (FDS). The image was automatically brightened by 40% and then reprocessed by the FDS. The face is now detectable (highlighted in green in the image on the right) and can be blurred. Section 3.3.3 describes how this finding could be used to improve the QA performance.

Figure 8: example of image brightening and the effect on the FDS accuracy. [Left] Original image (with actual face obscured by yellow star to preserve privacy) – no faces detected. [Centre] Image with brightness increased by 40%. [Right] Output of FDS on brightened image with green boxes highlighting successful face detection

3.2.3 Image size and resolution

The size and resolution of an image can have an impact on its quality. Low resolution images lack detail and can appear grainy. Small images, unless they are taken at high resolution, will also lose clarity when enlarged. Image resolution and size are functions of the camera used to take the image rather than the environmental conditions at the time it was taken. For this reason, checks on image size and resolution were not included in the LandSense QA platform, as this may have biased the contributions to exclude those collected by users with less expensive mobile devices. Although checks on image size and resolution were not performed as a formal part of the LandSense QA processes, their effect on image quality can be significant and may need to be considered in the development of QA services in the future.

In addition to reducing overall image quality, poor image resolution and size could potentially reduce the accuracy of privacy checks in a similar way to that described for image brightness in the previous section. To test this hypothesis, images collected from LandSense pilots that failed a privacy check were used. Image resolution and size were increased using upscaling algorithms, and privacy checks were then performed on the up-scaled images. As shown in Figure 9, increasing the image resolution (from 72dpi to 300dpi) and processing it through the LandSense FDS produced a more accurate result, with the 300dpi version (shown on the right) detecting four faces in comparison to the original image in which only two faces were detected. It may, therefore, be appropriate for good practice advice to include consideration of image size and resolution when performing privacy checks. This concept is further discussed in section 3.3.3.

Figure 9: Example of the effect of image resolution on face detection accuracy. [Left] original image processed through the FDS showing two potential faces (highlighted in green). [Right] Results from the FDS of processing Image up scaled to 300dpi showing four potential faces

3.3 Privacy checks on photo data

The aim of photo privacy checks is to ensure the anonymity of people captured in photos taken as part of the pilot campaigns. This means that visible faces and the license plates of vehicles (which could be linked to an individual) must be obscured. It should be noted that images taken as part of the LandSense project, or a similar citizen science observatory, vary greatly based on the types of observations that each pilot is collecting. For example, the majority of CropSupport imagery is of agricultural land and fields of growing crops, whereas images taken by the City.Oases pilot are primarily of urban scenes. The likelihood of people

and vehicles in the latter is much greater than in the former. However, in both instances, images of people and vehicles are not the primary focus of the images taken. Therefore, in the majority of cases, any faces and/or license plates present could be in the background of the image and could be some distance from the camera. As discussed in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020), these are referred to as unconstrained images in the image recognition literature and have a much lower success rate for detecting privacy features (Yang et al, 2016; Silva and Jung, 2018) than often quoted for the automated machine learning based techniques used in this context. In contrast, constrained images, where the likely position, scale or angle of the feature(s) to be detected is known in advance, are a simpler problem and can produce very high (90%+) detection rates. For unconstrained images, Yang et al. (2016) suggests that accuracy rates of around 70% for detecting faces in images would be considered a reasonable performance.

Another complication is the actual definition of success and failure in the context of privacy checks. This is not as simple and binary a decision as it may initially appear. For example, it may seem straightforward to define failure as being the presence of any undetected privacy feature after the privacy check has been performed. However, if the feature was not clearly visible in the original image, due to its distance from the camera or being partially obscured, then some judgement is required to determine whether the feature needed to be removed to maintain the subject's anonymity. Figure 10 and Figure 11 provide examples where failure to detect features meant that these were classed as failures but it is arguable that the features in these images are not clearly visible and it would be very difficult, if not impossible, to identify the people and vehicles in these images.

A similar, but less critical, issue also applies to errors of commission (i.e., images where a privacy feature was detected but either did not exist or was not clearly visible in the original image). Figure 12 gives examples of this type of failure. Commission errors are defined as a failure of the privacy check, but depending on project requirements, some level of commission error is likely to be acceptable in order to minimise the likelihood of omission errors. However, excessive levels of commission error reduce the quality of the photo submissions and potentially remove the object of interest from the photo. This was found to be an issue with the face detection service in the CropSupport pilot study and is further described in section 3.3.1.

Figure 10: Examples of images where face is present in image but not clearly visible. Classed as a failure but it is arguable as to whether the people in these images are actually recognisable

Figure 11: Example of image where license plates are present but not detected although angle and distance of license plates to the camera makes it ambiguous as to whether the license plate is clearly visible and recognisable

Figure 12: Examples of commission errors. [Left] face detection service incorrectly detected four faces in this image when only one (figure on right) is actually visible. The other three figures are facing away from the camera, with only the back of their heads visible [Right] License plate detection service incorrectly identifies and blurs portion of signage on a container as a license plate

It is important to highlight that no automated privacy check is capable of 100% accurate detection (Liao et al, 2014). Therefore, if it is critical (e.g., for GDPR requirements) that all privacy features are identified, then some level of manual intervention will be required. For citizen observatories like LandSense, one option could be to use citizen contributors to provide manual feedback on the presence of privacy features in an image as a post-processing step in any QA privacy check procedure.

A potential model for such manual interventions was explored during the LandSense project and described in deliverable D5.6 (Long et al., 2020). In that instance, IIASA’s Picture Pile software (Danylo et al., 2018) was used to pre-filter the City.Oases dataset of photos (~1800 images) to exclude all images that did not require privacy checks. The same process could be employed as a post-privacy check to ensure that all privacy features have been successfully identified and anonymised.

Another option explored by the City.Oases pilot was for contributors to identify any privacy features manually during the image upload process in the pilot app. In the upload page, the users are asked to blur out parts of the images which could identify a person, license plate or private property before they upload them (Figure 13 [right]). When the users click the Edit button on the upload page, they get to the edit page (Figure 13 [left]) on which they can select an image. When the user has selected an image, they can blur out parts of the image by touching the points on the image that should be blurred (Figure 13 [top]). It should be noted that this manual privacy check, as with the automated detection service, is not 100% accurate. QA checks on the City.Oases image library found a number of images where manual blurring had failed to identify privacy features, and these were then processed using the LandSense QA privacy check services. Details of this were outlined in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020).

Figure 13: City.Oases App screenshots illustrating options for manual blurring of privacy features

3.3.1 Face detection service (FDS)

The performance of the LandSense Face Detection Service (FDS) was discussed in detail in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020) and will not be repeated here. To summarise, it was found that the FDS performed well for clearly visible faces but struggled where faces were obscured, poorly lit or were in the background of the image. The overall performance of the FDS seems to match the level of accuracy quoted in the literature (Yang et al., 2016) for the types of unconstrained imagery collected by LandSense, i.e., around 70%. Examples of common failure types were shown in the previous section (see Figure 10 and Figure 12), which highlighted the difficulty in assessing detection failure in images where faces are not clearly visible. Almost half of the 49 detection failures of the FDS can be categorised as borderline cases where it is arguable whether any faces in the image were clearly recognisable and needed to be blurred.

Performance across the different pilot studies and themes showed a significant degree of variance, with the urban-based pilots showing the highest level of omission errors, mainly due to the increased presence of people in the images collected. Commission errors were more common in the agricultural and habitat-monitoring pilots, with the CropSupport pilot, in particular, showing a high degree of commission errors. One potential method to improve overall FDS performance would be to use differentiated detection thresholds based on the probability and prevalence of faces in the images collected. This hypothesis was examined in section 5 (see section 5.2) of D5.6 (Long et al., 2020), which showed how a higher threshold value for the CropSupport pilot study greatly reduced the number of commission errors.

Retraining the FDS using the images collected by the LandSense pilots was an option investigated, but it was determined there would not be significant improvement in performance since it is already at a level matching the state-of-the-art in face detection for unconstrained photographs. Despite this, the retraining option could be employed where error rates were above average or where varying the detection threshold had no impact on performance. Also, as with any machine learning algorithm, retraining must be carefully performed to ensure that the retrained model shows genuine improvement. Retraining using the images collected by LandSense may improve detection rates for those specific images, but it could introduce new types of failure when used on other images.

As discussed in section 3.2, no automated privacy check is infallible in all cases. A number of options for how manual checks could be integrated into a FDS were assessed, including pre-processing filtering and post-processing verification. Pre-processing filtering is applicable where images are collected and then processed in bulk after collection. It can be used to reduce the overall processing time, although it should be noted that a manual post-process verification check will still be required if 100% accuracy is needed. The LandSense FDS takes around 10-20 seconds to process an image depending on the image resolution and the number of potential faces present in the image. Where many images are being collected as part of a pilot, this can lead to long processing times. For example, 1833 photographs were collected with City.Oases, with users identifying and blurring privacy features, as shown in Figure 13. The LandSense FDS was then used to remove any faces not identified by users during the data collection. However, to process all 1833 images would have taken between 5-10 hours of processing time. Manually pre-filtering the images using IASA's Picture Pile software reduced the number of images for processing from 1833 to 192, reducing the processing time to

30-60 minutes. This type of filtering process could be carried out by contributors after the initial data collection phase.

If 100% accuracy is needed, for example, to comply fully with GDPR regulations, then some form of post-process manual verification check must be carried out. This could be performed by the QA team, pilot data manager or by the contributors themselves, using a Google Maps Local Guides type of approach as described for pre-process filtering. If GDPR regulations are the primary motivation for privacy checks, care must be taken to ensure that the regulations are not breached as part of the manual verification process itself. Any images that could potentially be in breach of the GDPR should not be located on a publicly accessible server until the QA FDS process is fully complete.

3.3.2 License plate detection

As described in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020), LandSense’s implementation of the License Plate Detection Service (LPDS) used the Open Source version of the OpenALPR algorithm as described by Masood et al. (2017). Its overall performance for the photo data collected appears, on initial examination, to be very high (97%), but the accuracy is inflated due to the low number of license plates visible in the images. If its accuracy is based solely on the images with visible license plates, then it only recognises one license plate out of the 38 in total. As with the FDS, many of the license plate failures are borderline cases where the vehicle’s license plate is not clearly visible, and it is debatable whether any LPDS would have been able to detect it accurately. To examine this, images from the City.Oases pilot, which had the largest number of license plates present, were evaluated using other LPDS.

The City.Oases pilot had 14 images with license plates present that were not detected by the LandSense LPDS. These images were reprocessed using the commercial version of OpenALPR⁵, which offers improved performance over the open source version used by LandSense. Even using this version, only 5 of the 14 images showed improved license plate detection (Figure 14). Figure 15 shows examples of images where the commercial LPDS cannot detect license plates.

⁵ <https://www.openalpr.com/>

Figure 14: City.Oases images where commercially licensed license plate detection service performed better than LandSense version (detected licence plates highlighted in purple)

Another commercial LPDS, PlateRecogniser (<https://platerecognizer.com>), was also tested using the 14 City.Oases license plate detection failures. Its performance was identical to the Commercial version of OpenALPR detecting the same license plates shown in Figure 14. Applying PlateRecogniser to the other detection failures from the LandSense pilots showed similar results, with some exceptions (Figure 16 & Figure 17) where PlateRecogniser managed to identify license plates not detected by the commercial version of OpenALPR.

Figure 15: Examples of images with vehicle license plates present and not detected by LandSense or commercial versions of OpenALPR

Figure 16: Image from the Paysages pilot showing performance differences between the two commercial LPDS tested. In both images, the license plates have been obscured to maintain privacy. [Left] Results from commercial version of OpenALPR with detected license plate highlighted in pink, [Right] Results from PlateRecogniser LPDS showing additional license plate detected highlighted in blue

Figure 17: Images where PlateRecogniser detected license plates not identified by the LandSense LPDS or the commercial version of OpenALPR. Note the presence of a commission error related to the construction signage on the right hand side of the image on the left. License plates detected are highlighted in blue with the actual license plates obscured to maintain privacy

Based on the detection rate using the commercial version of OpenALPR and PlateRecogniser, it is clear that the performance of the LandSense LPDS could be improved through further training. However, it is also clear that even with training, some license plates will not be identifiable due to the unconstrained nature of the images collected.

It is also questionable as to whether the license plates of the vehicles in many of the detection failures would actually be clearly visible enough to identify the specific vehicles, even upon close inspection. To illustrate this point, close up images of the two detection failures shown in Figure 15 are shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19. In the first instance (Figure 18), although a little blurred, it is potentially possible to identify the license plates. Conversely in Figure 19, even in close up, the license plates cannot be identified due to their angle to the camera and the lighting.

Figure 18: Zoomed in image of license plate ‘failures’ shown in Figure 15 [left]

Figure 19: Zoomed in image of license plate ‘failures’ shown in Figure 15 [right]

It is possible to retrain the OpenALPR algorithm to improve the performance. However, retraining is not a simple process and requires a large set of representative images to be used as a training set for the retraining process. The low number of images with license plates in the LandSense dataset would not be sufficient for retraining. Suitable images would need to be sourced for retraining the algorithm. In addition, it is debatable whether the cost of retraining the LPDS would be a worthwhile use of time and resources given the low prevalence of license plates in the data collected, and there would be no guarantee that any improvement would be significant given the performance of the commercial LPDS.

Due to the apparent difficulty in producing an LPDS providing sufficient detection capability, an alternative option would be to employ a commercial third party LPDS to perform this privacy check. Depending on the volume of images to be processed, the cost of this option may be more efficient than developing an in-house LPDS, even assuming that the in-house detection accuracy could match a commercial offering. For example, the PlateRecogniser LPDS, which performed better than both the LandSense OpenALPR implementation and the commercial version of OpenALPR, allows users to process 2,500 images per month for no cost⁶.

3.3.3 A revised good practice workflow for privacy checks on photographs

Improvements to photo quality such as image brightening and upscaling have been shown (in sections 3.2.2 and 3.2.3) to be able to improve the accuracy of privacy checks. Therefore, performing photo quality checks prior to privacy checking should be able to provide some indication of the potential accuracy of privacy checks. Further to this, photo quality improvements could be made to the original images prior to privacy

⁶ See <https://platerecognizer.com/pricing/> [checked 29/08/20]

checking to maximise the accuracy of the privacy check. The locations of privacy features in the altered images could then be applied to the original unprocessed images to ensure that the original images collected are used, with the privacy features removed. Figure 20 shows a revised image processing QA workflow where photo quality checks are integrated with privacy checks.

Figure 20: Revised image processing workflow integrating photo quality checking into privacy checks to maximise privacy check accuracy

3.4 QA checks for positional accuracy and offset

Positional accuracy is very important in the collection of data on LULC (Congalton and Green, 2019). Many analyses of data, for instance, assume high positional accuracy, and hence, it is important to establish the level of accuracy required and that achieved. The measurement of positional accuracy and offset are relatively straightforward and have been extensively described in previous deliverables (see for example D5.2 (Schultz, 2018) and D5.4 (Rosser and Schultz, 2019)). In terms of good practice, the definition of accuracy and offset requirements is the key issue to be discussed here. In line with the other QA services discussed, the context of the data collection exercise being undertaken is a critical element in the definition of positional accuracy requirements. The scale of the LULC feature being surveyed will significantly constrain the level of positional accuracy required for the user observation point. The density of observation points within a given area will also affect the level of positional accuracy required. To illustrate this, where areas being observed

are large, open land use features, such as fields of crops for the CropSupport pilot, the degree of positional accuracy for the observation point does not need to be high to be of sufficient quality. In contrast, where the features being observed are small and densely packed, as with individual areas within urban green spaces, like those observed in the Mijnpark.NL pilot, a higher level of positional accuracy may be required to ensure that the contributor has observed the correct LULC feature.

The local environment will influence the level of positional accuracy that can be achieved. In urban locations, the presence of tall buildings and other obstructions to a clear view of the sky will reduce positional accuracy, as described in D5.6 (Long et al., 2020). Observations taken in more open, rural or suburban locations, such as the CropSupport pilot, will not suffer from similar GPS signal quality issues. In addition to climatic and locational factors, the technical specifications of the mobile device used to make the observations could affect the degree of positional accuracy obtainable. Studies on location tracking using mobile devices have shown horizontal accuracies ranging from 5-15m (Merry and Bettinger, 2019; Menard et al., 2011). Newer devices tend to demonstrate higher positional accuracy. For example, Zandbergen (2009) found an average horizontal positional error of 10m for the iPhone 3G. This was reduced to 6.5m for the iPhone 4S according to Garnett and Stewart (2015). The technical capability of typical mobile devices that will be used in data collection should be considered when assessing the degree of positional accuracy that can be achieved. This may influence the design of any data collection exercise.

For guided campaigns, where both positional accuracy of the observation point and its positional offset from the reference point are important, the previous factors are potentially even more critical. The combination of errors of positional accuracy and offset can lead to large disparities in the spatial accuracy of the observations. For this reason, guided campaigns, in particular, should integrate the likely spatial accuracy of the mobile devices used to collect data in their design. A guided campaign should also consider the likelihood of obstructions to GPS signals and their potential impact on positional accuracy when choosing the location of observation points.

One potential method for reducing spatial accuracy issues in a guided campaign might be to consider the use of technological solutions to reduce or eliminate the positional offset problem. For example, QR codes could be installed at the observation points, and users could be required to scan the code to indicate that they are at the correct location. Obviously, this option would require the presence of some physical infrastructure to which the QR code can be attached (e.g., post, bench, tree, etc.). Another technological solution could be the installation of Bluetooth beacons at the observation points that could then log the presence of a Bluetooth enabled phone at the location and inform the user via the pilot app that they were in the correct location.

When considering an appropriate level of positional offset for guided campaigns, it may be considered good practice to allow variable offset thresholds. For the LandSense guided campaigns (Mijnpark.NL, City.Oases), a fixed value of 20m for positional offset was used, as both pilots were collecting data in similar urban environments. However, it would be possible to vary the offset based on the observability of each observation point (i.e., the positional offset threshold could be relaxed for large features and tightened for small features or ones that need to be viewed from a specific spatial point). As elsewhere, the good practice

advice is that settings such as offset thresholds should be selected based on the requirements of a particular application.

3.5 QA checks for contributor agreement

The QA checks for contributor agreement seek to determine the extent to which two or more citizens participating in a project agree on the labelling of cases. There is interest, for example, in whether two or more contributors allocate the same LULC class to a site. Agreement occurs when the same label is allocated to a case, but disagreement occurs if the labels allocated are dissimilar. This activity has some similarity to the QA checks for categorical accuracy discussed in section 3.6 below, but important differences exist that necessitate separate discussion. In particular, with an accuracy assessment, the focus is on whether the contributed data agrees with reality (i.e., the allocated label is that which actually applies and can be considered to be the ‘truth’), whereas with contributor agreement, the focus is on whether the contributors agree in labelling; it is perfectly possible, for example, for contributors to agree but be incorrect relative to reality.

Contributor agreement was an issue in a set of LandSense pilot studies. The core focus in LandSense applications was typically either upon agreement on labelling to conventional LULC classes (e.g., OSMLanduse, Paysages) or to classes that indicate the perception of places (e.g., City.Oases, MijPark.NL). A basis for assessing contributor agreement is similar to that suggested for accuracy assessment in remote sensing (Congalton and Green, 2019) with the notable exception that the true label for each case is not considered. The basic approach has three main components: response design, sampling design and analysis (Stehman and Czaplewski, 1998).

The response design contains all steps that lead to a decision regarding agreement between two or more sets of contributed label data. This includes specification on exactly what is being labelled, the labelling protocol, and the definition of agreement to be used. Thus, for example, it is important that there is clear and unambiguous guidance on the task so that the contributors understand exactly what the task is, the options open to them, and that a suitable method is used to assess their agreement. These various issues can be non-trivial, and hence, clear guidance and supporting documentation may be required. For example, in the seemingly simple task of allocating a LULC class label to a building, it must be clear what an individual building is (e.g., is it a discrete detached feature or can there be spatially joined buildings? This distinction can be significant, for instance, in residential areas where the distinction between detached and terraced housing may be important). The classes to be used must also be clear and the classification scheme used should ideally be exhaustive and able to address common problems such as cases that may involve a mixture of classes (e.g., contributors instructed to label the dominant class). Finally, an appropriate analysis is required to provide meaningful information on the level of agreement that exists between the data provided by the contributors. Issues such as sampling design (e.g., the locations at which labels are acquired) should be considered, especially if seeking to generalise the results, but as this is an issue of greater concern to the assessment of categorical accuracy, it is discussed more fully in section 3.6 below; here the focus is simply on the degree of agreement between two or more contributors for a specific data set.

A key part of the response design is the labelling protocol, and this can be challenging as many class definitions often exist (e.g., Comber et al. 2005, 2008; Ahlquist 2008). In LandSense, this challenge is also sometimes magnified, as highly subjective phenomena related to perceptions of place were studied. It is critical that a clear and unambiguous set of classes are defined and that all of the contributors can use these labels effectively. To help achieve this situation, the response design should include means to enhance the consistency in labelling (Olofsson et al., 2014), perhaps by provision of supporting documentation (e.g., classification keys, examples) and training in labelling. It may also be useful to acquire self-confidence ratings in labelling (e.g., Comber et al., 2014) to help filter a data set, although these can be problematic as poor contributors may over-estimate their abilities (Ehrlinger et al., 2008).

Given a set of contributed labels for any case, rules for defining agreement need to be specified before proceeding to the analysis stage and quantifying agreement. Often a simple situation will exist in which the class labels provided by the contributors are the same, and hence, they agree, or the labels differ, and hence, they disagree. However, as noted above, there is sometimes a need to accommodate for challenges such as when two or more labels may apply to a case. It is important to ensure that the contributors are labelling the same geographical feature. In LandSense, a key aid to this is to ensure geolocation and hence tools such as the positional accuracy test (see Section 3.4) can usefully aid categorical assessment.

The assessment of contributor agreement is based upon the comparison of labels produced by the contributors for a set of cases. In the basic scenario involving two contributors, agreement is often assessed by cross-tabulating the labels from the contributors. On the assumption that the same classification scheme has been used, cases lying in the main diagonal of the cross-tabulation matrix show agreement while off-diagonal cases show disagreement. A very large number of measures may be used to quantify the level of agreement. A measure needs to be selected to meet the aims of the study and should be appropriate for the data available. Popular approaches used to indicate overall agreement are the proportion of cases upon which contributors agree (i.e., the number of cases of agreement divided by the total number of cases labelled) and the kappa coefficient of agreement (Congalton et al., 1983; Congalton and Green, 2019). Agreement may also be calculated from the matrices on a per-class basis, for example, by focusing on the number of cases of agreement divided by the total number of cases labelled by the relevant contributor. In situations when agreement by more than two contributors is being assessed, it may be possible to use a measure such as Fleiss's kappa (Fleiss, 1971). The calculation of the latter involves the computation of the extent to which contributors agree for an individual case, and this was used in OSMLanduse, Paysages, and MijnPark.NL – based on calculation of P_i , where P_i is the degree to which the contributors agree for the i^{th} subject.

In the course of the LandSense project, some challenges and issues were encountered. Two are highlighted here. First, there were instances in which data were obtained by only one contributor. In such circumstances, agreement between contributors cannot be assessed. It may, however, be possible to evaluate other aspects of the quality of the data. For example, it may be possible to determine how the contributed data fits within its geographical context (Goodchild and Li, 2012) or to compare the labels against some other source of data. Second, in many instances a large number of contributors may participate. For example, in LandSense, between 2 to 40 contributors provided data for MijnPark.NL and from 3 to 6 for contributors for Paysages

for the same location. Sometimes the number of participants may be so large that it actually degrades the quality of information from their contributions (Foody et al., 2015). In such circumstances, a range of possible approaches may be used to maximise the value of the data. For example, attention could focus on cases for which all, or a majority, of contributors agree. Information on contributor performance may also be used to weight contributed data (Foody et al., 2018). Other projects have suggested that a set of between 3-15 contributors is often sufficient in the acquisition of VGI (Haklay et al., 2010; Foody et al., 2015), although the range is likely to be application dependent, and it would be good practice to strive for such a community in future work. However, in doing so, the composition of the crowd needs attention (Comber et al., 2016). Within LandSense, for example, contributors with different motivational profiles performed differently (Olteanu-Raimond et al., 2020), and this may have implications for future studies, especially in relation to issues such as the selection and training of potential contributors.

3.6 QA checks for categorical accuracy

In this section, the concern is, essentially, on the thematic or attribute accuracy of labelling provided by contributors. Although there is some similarity with the assessment of contributor agreement discussed in section 3.5 above, there are important differences, notably that the assessment involves comparison to reality or truth (i.e., a gold standard reference data set).

Accuracy assessment was an issue in a set of LandSense pilot studies, primarily OSMLanduse, but also for elements of the Paysages pilot. Good practices for accuracy assessment exist, especially in a remote sensing context that are highly relevant to LandSense (Olofsson et al., 2014). As discussed in relation to the assessment of agreement, the basic approach has three main components: response design, sampling design and analysis (Stehman and Czaplewski, 1998).

The response design contains all steps that lead to a decision regarding agreement between the contributed data and reality or truth contained in a reference data set. As in the assessment of agreement, key issues are the specification on exactly what is being labelled, the labelling protocol and the definition of agreement to be used. However, in addition, sampling issues and the nature of the reference data set often require attention.

As in the assessment of agreement, there is a need to define clearly and unambiguously what is being labelled. In some LandSense applications, the focus is on labelling of remote sensing imagery, often obtained via an image classification analysis. In such circumstances, there is a need to define the spatial unit of the accuracy assessment. This feature is central to the popular site-specific approach to accuracy assessment (Congalton and Green, 2019). In this approach to accuracy assessment, the analysis is based upon a comparison of the contributed class label and that which exists in reality and is contained in the reference data set. It is therefore, helpful, but not essential, that the same spatial unit is used, highlighting the importance of ensuring geolocation and the potential value of the positional accuracy tool (section 3.4 above). Unfortunately, a pixel is an arbitrary spatial unit and it may sometimes be preferable to use something else such as a land parcel or field. Differences in the spatial unit can be accommodated, but the analysis should recognise this issue. Land parcels are typically polygonal features and may be obtained in some practical applications via a segmentation analysis. There are many methods and challenges in

segmenting an image optimally (Costa et al., 2018), and it may be helpful to ensure that the reference data and polygon of interest spatially overlap using a tool such as the polygon check (section 3.1 above). Whatever spatial unit is used, it is common to find that class mixing occurs. For example, mixed pixels may be common as it is an artificial unit that may not provide a realistic representation of the land mosaic (Foody, 1996; Fisher, 1997), but mixed objects are also commonly encountered (Costa et al., 2017).

Irrespective of the specific spatial unit chosen for use in an accuracy assessment, a critical feature of the response design is that the spatially explicit character of the analysis be retained. Good practice advice (Olofsson et al., 2014) calls for the reference data to have an equal or finer level of detail than the data used to generate the thematic map being assessed and provides further discussion of unit-specific recommendations.

Given the importance of the reference data that are taken to indicate reality to an accuracy assessment, their nature and properties need consideration. The reference data set is often used implicitly as a gold standard reference, yet it rarely is, and deviation from this assumption can result in substantial mis-estimation (Foody, 2009a; 2010). A key consideration with the reference data is its source of origin and quality. The reference data may often arise from volunteers (Laso Bayas et al., 2017; Waldner et al., 2019) as well as experts, and in remote sensing studies, often involves either fieldwork or the interpretation of aerial photography or satellite imagery of the region mapped. Good practice advice (Olofsson et al., 2014) urges that the reference data be of higher quality than the map being evaluated. This typically requires that the source of the reference data be of higher quality than which was used to form the map or that the process to form the reference data was more accurate than that used to form the map being evaluated.

Central to the assessment is a labelling protocol that contains the steps in the response design that take the information provided by the reference data and convert that information to the label constituting the reference classification (Olofsson et al., 2014). This labelling task is non-trivial, especially with many definitions existing for classes (Comber et al., 2008) although interoperability and the ability to translate from one set of labels to another has been enhanced in recent years (Ahlqvist, 2008). An additional feature of the labelling protocol is the specification of a minimum mapping unit (MMU) for the reference data. The latter can have important implications for accuracy assessment. The MMU will, for instance, impact greatly on the representation of highly fragmented landscapes (Saura, 2002) and changing it can also influence accuracy estimates (Knight and Lunetta, 2003). In general, very small land cover patches will be poorly represented and increasingly so as the MMU is increased. As such, the MMU should be selected with care for the application in-hand. The MMU adopted for the response design does not have to equal that used for the map being assessed.

The simplest scenario for the labelling protocol occurs when the assessment unit is homogeneous, and a single reference class label can be assigned. Unfortunately, the task is often more challenging with, for example, the units under study being of mixed class composition. In such instances, there needs to be clear and well-defined rules to allow progress. For example, a mixed unit could be allocated the dominant class label. Alternatively, a fuzzy reference labelling protocol could be used such as in the linguistic scale devised by Gopal and Woodcock (1994) or a fuzzy approach to accuracy assessment adopted (Foody, 1996; Binaghi et al., 1999).

Once the contributed and reference classifications have been obtained for a given case, rules for defining agreement must be specified before proceeding to the analyses to quantify accuracy. As in assessing contributor agreement, the simplest case occurs when a single class label is associated with both data sets, the contributed and reference data. Given that the reference data represent reality, in the situation in which the two labels agree, the contributed data are correct or accurate. Conversely, in the situation in which the contributed data disagree with the reference data label, the contributed data are incorrect or inaccurate. In situation in which two or more labels may be associated with one or more of the data sets, an alternative approach is needed such as those discussed above.

In an accuracy assessment, a fundamental assumption is that the reference data set represent the ground truth (i.e., a “gold standard” reference data set). However, this is rarely the case. Error inevitably exists, and it is important to recognise that error in the reference data set, even in small amounts, can substantially degrade an analysis (Foody, 2010; 2013). A range of error sources can be identified (Foody, 2002; 2008). As noted above, common error sources such as spatial mis-registration (Pontius, 2000) can be reduced using positional accuracy tools, and the response design should aim to minimise such errors. Error can rarely be eradicated, but it is important to note that it is sometimes possible to use information on data quality if known to adjust estimates (Foody, 2011).

Sometimes the reference data comes from multiple interpreters (Wulder et al., 2007; Wickham et al., 2013). In such cases, it is common to focus on only a subset of the cases. For example, sometimes it may be appropriate to use only the cases upon which interpreters agree (Scepan, 1999). In other instances, it may be appropriate to use a consensus label for each case. Care must be taken to ensure an appropriate approach is adopted. For example, by focusing on only cases of complete agreement, a data set may be limited to relatively unrepresentative sample locations of simple homogenous composition. It is also common for disagreements to be largest for rare classes (Wulder et al., 2007; Stehman and Foody, 2019) and so by ignoring such cases, a study may end up excluding rare classes by accident.

In many scenarios, the sampling design used to acquire the data upon which the accuracy assessment is to be based is of critical importance. If the aim is to not merely consider the accuracy with which a particular testing set has been classified and there is a desire to generalize, such as to an entire map, then good practice guidelines call for the use of a probability sample design (Olofsson et al., 2014). Many sample designs may be used, notably simple random, stratified, cluster and systematic (Stehman, 1999), and guidance on the selection for different study objectives is provided in the literature (Stehman, 2009). Of key concern for typical LandSense-type applications is that if there is a desire to assess the accuracy of a LULC map, a probability sample should be used and its properties considered in the estimation of accuracy (Olofsson et al., 2014). Thus, for example, if a stratified sample design is used, the size of the strata should be accommodated in the estimation of map accuracy or phenomena such as class areal extent (Olofsson et al., 2013). The required sample size can be estimated from sampling theory (Foody, 2009b), and is important in influencing the width of the confidence interval that may be fitted to the estimates. Alternatively, simple heuristics, such as a minimum of 50 cases per class (Hay, 1979), may be adopted if appropriate. Note that data from a non-probability sample, as may occur with some VGI, can be usefully integrated with such data to enhance analyses (Stehman et al., 2018).

Finally, the cross-tabulation of the map label against the reference label yields an error or confusion matrix from which a set of measures of accuracy may be estimated. There are many measures of accuracy that can be calculated from the confusion matrix (Card, 1982). The latter include measures of overall accuracy (i.e., measures the proportion of all classes that were correctly classified based on the reference data) as well as measures for individual classes (i.e., measures the proportion of correct classifications of a given class based on the reference data). Many of the measures used in the assessment of contributor agreement (section 3.5) may be used, but care is needed, as not all are suited for use in an accuracy assessment. The kappa coefficient, for example, is suited for use in measuring contributor agreement but not to accuracy assessment (Pontius and Millones, 2011; Foody, 2020). Widely used measures of accuracy include the proportion of correctly labelled cases, often referred to as overall accuracy, and user's and producer's accuracy for per-class assessments (Card, 1982). As the assessment is typically based upon a sample of cases, good practice would be to fit confidence limits to the estimate to indicate the uncertainty of the estimate obtained (Olofsson et al., 2014).

There are many challenges in accuracy assessment and other approaches may sometimes be suitable. For example, if the map and reference data legends do not match or perhaps contain a different number of classes, then alternative methods, such as those based on entropy, may be undertaken (Finn, 1993; Foody, 2006; Salk et al., 2018). Good practice advice would be to ensure that all key assumptions are satisfied. For example, it is typically assumed that classes are discrete and mutually exclusive, yet this may be inappropriate for regions where classes are continuous and intergrade. It is also often assumed that the set of classes has been defined exhaustively. This may not always be the case. For example, comparison of the crop map produced by Sonobe et al. (2017) against the FROMGLC map, which provides a representation of the land cover at a broadly comparable format, suggests that over a third of the mapped area is covered with a class beyond the training set used to form the classifier. This comparison will be imperfect, but the size of the area covered by untrained classes is large. This latter situation will result in the accuracy assessment not relating well to the map. Sometimes, it may be necessary to deviate from good practices, and if this is the case, open and honest reporting of the accuracy assessment is required to aid interpretation (Stehman and Foody, 2019). Other approaches to indicate accuracy, such as those based on social status and geographical context may also be used to help support an accuracy assessment (Goodchild and Li, 2012).

4 Benchmarking

Authoritative national and continental land use products were compared to a citizen science-based land use product (OSMlanduse) to identify similarities. This comparison serves as a benchmark test for citizen science derived land use mapping. For each pilot city shown in Figure 21, the respective available national authoritative data were translated to the European Coordination of Information on the Environment (CORINE) Land Cover (CLC) legend level 2 (necessary as OSMlanduse is available only for CLC level 2). Given legend harmonization limitations in some cases, CLC level 1 was used (Section 4.1). Descriptive statistics and spatially explicit product differencing were then used to compare the product overlaps and class conflation (Sections 4.2.1, 4.2.2, and 4.2.3).

Figure 21: Location and boundaries of the pilot cities involved: Heidelberg (HEI), Toulouse (TLS) and Vienna (VIE)

4.1 Benchmark method

This section describes the method proposed to define the benchmarks. It focuses on comparing the OSMlanduse.org product built in LandSense (Schultz et al., 2017) with authoritative LULC datasets for each country (Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS)⁷ in Germany, OCS-GE⁸ for France, and Realnutzung for Austria), and with the CLC map for each city. For each pilot city, the national product, OSMlanduse and the CLC map were compared. For the Toulouse case study, two NMA datasets were compared against OSMlanduse as, unlike the other two cities, the OCS-GE dataset included both LULC data. In total, seven comparisons were performed using six maps against the citizen science sourced OSMlanduse map (as shown in Table 2).

⁷ <https://gdz.bkg.bund.de/index.php/default/digitale-geodaten/digitale-landschaftsmodelle/digitales-landschaftsmodell-1-250-000-ebenen-dlm250-ebenen.html>

⁸ <http://professionnels.ign.fr/ocsge>

Table 2: List of datasets that were benchmarked against the citizen science sourced OSMLanduse LULC mapping data. There were six maps (one NMA and one CLC for each of the three case studies) with two comparisons made for the OCS-GE (Toulouse) map (one for LU data values and one for LC data values) making a total of seven benchmarking comparisons against the OSMLanduse data.

NMA	CORINE Land Cover (CLC)
ATKIS (Heidelberg)	CLC Heidelberg
OCS-GE (Toulouse) - Land Use data	CLC Toulouse
OCS-GE (Toulouse) – Land Cover data	
Realnutzung (Vienna)	CLC Vienna

For the comparison, we clipped the maps of each city to the largest common area shared between the NMA, OSMLanduse and CLC datasets. In most instances, this would be the extent of the NMA mapping dataset. To resolve differences regarding the minimum mapping unit (MMU), each map was resampled to a 10m grid using a nearest neighbour resampling technique. The legends were harmonized as displayed in Table 2. The resampled datasets were compared to identify areas of agreement and areas where there were thematic and spatial disparities, i.e., where there were differences between the LULC classification for a given area and the extent of spatial differences between the datasets. This is further explained in the description of the difference maps produced for each case study in section 4.3.1.

4.1.1 Legend harmonization

Table 3 shows the legend harmonization and LULC legends used by all datasets involved in the benchmarking case studies. Legends were harmonized in collaboration with representatives of the various national authorities (e.g., the Umweltbundesamt Vienna regarding the Austrian map) and following the recommendations outlined in the Land Cover Classification System (LCCS) (di Gregorio and Jansen, 2000) to CLC. Additionally, classes 4.1 (Inland wetland) and 4.2 (Coastal wetland) as well as any 5.0 (water bodies) class were combined within class 5.0. Class 2.4 (Heterogeneous agricultural areas) was only available for a few pixels and merged with class 2.1 (Arable land). Data for Germany were only available for a limited region, which contained only a sub-set of the full class legend. Hence, large parts of the legend harmonization could only be established towards CLC level 1 (see Table 3).

The French OCS-GE LULC product was available from a land cover and a land use perspective (i.e., for each mapping unit, there were data attributes for both the land use of the unit and the land cover). For some classes, the translation was limited to CLC level 1 (Table 3). Moreover, some of the corresponding links are direct links while others are indirect, as the OSMLanduse product has mixed LU and LC classes. For example, land cover classes (CS1.1.1.1 Built-up areas and CS 1.1.1.2. Non built-up areas) are indirectly linked to OSMLanduse classes: 1.1-Urban fabric and 1.2-Industrial, commercial and transport, which represent the use of soils. For some other classes, the links are n: 1 (i.e., n land cover classes of the OCS-GE correspond to one

land cover class of the OSMLanduse product). This is the case, for example, for CS 1.1.2.1 - Areas with mineral materials and CS 1.1.2.2- Areas with other composite materials, which are linked to the same land cover class 1.3 - Mine, dump and construction sites. Concerning the harmonization of the legend between the OCS-GE and OSMLanduse land use classes, some of the corresponding links are direct links while others are indirect, as the OSMLanduse product has mixed the LU and LC classes. For example, land use class 1.4 (Aquaculture and fishing) of OCS-GE is indirectly linked to land use class 5.0 (Water bodies) of the product OSMLanduse. Indeed, aquaculture and fishing activities are possible only in water bodies. For some other classes, the links are n: 1 (i.e. n land use classes of the OCS-GE correspond to m land use classes of the OSMLanduse product). For example, Transportation network (4.1) and its lower levels of OCS-GE correspond to the same land use class in OSMLanduse (e.g., Industrial, commercial and transportation units) or the class 235 (Industrial, commercial and services, and residential) of OCS-GE that correspond to two classes (e.g. 1.2-Industrial, commercial and transportation units and 1.1-Urban fabric) in the OSMLanduse product. Finally, some land use classes of OCS-GE do not have a corresponding class in OSMLanduse (e.g., 6.2- Abandoned areas, 6.3-Not currently used, and 6.6- Unknown use).

The Austrian Realnutzung 2018 legend introduces a lot of ambiguity as residential classes and classes characterized by commercial/industrial usage are often mixed. For instance, “grossvolumiger, solitärer Wohn (misch) bau (high intensity solitary residential and mixed-use built-up)” is predominantly residential, and therefore, part of the urban class (1.1); however, it also includes elements of commercial use. More striking is that business, administration and residential land use are highly mixed. For instance, the classes Büro- und Verwaltungsviertel (office and administration quarters) and Geschäfts-, Kern- u. Mischgebiete (business and mixed used areas including central business districts) were linked to the urban fabric class, yet it is debatable whether it should be linked instead to the class Industrial commercial and transport units.

Table 3: Legend harmonization of CLC-based OSMLanduse legend towards digitale Landschaftskarte of Amtliches Topographisch-Kartographisches Informationssystem (ATKIS) 2018 (DE) for Heidelberg; OCS-GEO 2016 (FR) for Toulouse; Realnutzung 2018 (AU) for Vienna; CLC Legend 2018; * class 3.0 was used for Heidelberg exclusively towards the ATKIS comparison

<i>Class</i>	<i>CLC Class</i>	<i>CLC Class name/ OSMLanduse</i>	<i>digitales Landschaftsmodel (ATKIS) DE - Heidelberg</i>	<i>OCS-GE LU – FR Toulouse</i>	<i>OCS-GE LC – FR - Toulouse</i>	<i>Realnutzungskartierung 2018 Wien – AU- Vienna</i>
1	1.1	Urban fabric	sie02: AX_Siedlungsflaeche (areas of settlement)	US4.3 (Public utility networks); US6.1 (Construction zones); US235 (Industrial, Commercial and Services, and Residential)	CS 1.1.1.1 (Built-up areas)	Büro- und Verwaltungsviertel (office and administration quarters) Geschäfts-, Kern- u. Mischgebiete (business and mixed used areas including central business districts) Mischnutzung wenig dicht (sparsely distributed mixed use) solitäre Handelsstrukturen (solitary business instalments) Bildung (education) Gesundheit und Einsatzorg. (health and technical support units) Energieversorgung u. Rundfunkanlagen (power plants and power infrastructure including broadcasting infrastructure) Militärische Anlagen (Military facility) Wasserversorgung (water supply) dichtes Wohn(misch)gebiet (dense residential and mixed use areas) grossvolumiger, solitärer Wohn(misch)bau (high intensity solitary residential and mixed-use built-up) locker bebautes Wohn(misch)gebiet (sparsely residential and mixed use built up area) Wohn(misch)gebiet mittlerer Dichte (residential and mixed use area)

<i>Class</i>	<i>CLC Class</i>	<i>CLC Class name/OSMlanduse</i>	<i>digitales Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS) DE - Heidelberg</i>	<i>OCS-GE LU – FR Toulouse</i>	<i>OCS-GE LC – FR - Toulouse</i>	<i>Realnutzungskartierung 2018 Wien – AU- Vienna</i>
2	1.2	Industrial, commercial and transport units	sie02: AX_FlaecheBesonderer FunktionalerPraegung (special use areas), AX_IndustrieUndGewerbeflaeche (areas of industry and commerce)	US4.3 (Public utility networks); US6.1 (Construction zones); US235 (Industrial, Commercial and Services, and Residential); US4.1 (Transportation network); US4.1.1 (Road transport); US4.1.2 (Railway transport); US4.1.3 (Air transport), US4.1.4 (Water transport); US4.2 (Logistics and storage); US4.3 (Public utility networks)	CS 1.1.1.2 (Non-built-up areas)	Industrie, prod. Gewerbe, Grosshandel inkl. Lager (areas of industry and commerce, manufacturing including storage facilities) Strassenraum begrünt (street space with planted vegetation) Strassenraum unbegrünt (street spaces) Bahnhöfe und Bahnanlagen (railway stations and related facilities) Parkplätze u. Parkhäuser (parking spots and garages) Transport und Logistik inkl. Lager (transport infrastructure including logistic and storage facilities)

<i>Class</i>	<i>CLC Class</i>	<i>CLC Class name/OSMlanduse</i>	<i>digitales Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS) DE - Heidelberg</i>	<i>OCS-GE LU – FR Toulouse</i>	<i>OCS-GE LC – FR - Toulouse</i>	<i>Realnutzungskartierung 2018 Wien – AU- Vienna</i>
3	1.3	Mine, dump and construction sites	-	US4.3 (Public utility networks); US6.1 (Construction zones); US1.3 (Mining and quarrying)	CS 1.1.2.1 (Areas with mineral materials); CS 1.1.2.2 (Areas with other composite materials)	Kläranlage, Deponie (waste processing plants and waste storage) Transformationsfläche, Baustelle, Materialgew. (conversion areas, construction sites and quarries)
4	1.4	Artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas	-	US4.3 (Public utility networks); US6.1 (Construction zones)	-	Kultur, Freizeit, Messe (culture, entertainment and fair) Sport und Bad (Indoor) (indoor sport and swimming facilities) Friedhof (graveyards) Park, Grünanlage (parks and artificial vegetated areas) Sport und Bad (Outdoor), Camping (outdoor sport and swimming facilities including camp sites)
5	2.0	Agricultural areas	-	-	-	-
6	2.1	Arable land	veg01: AX_Landwirtschaft (Agriculture)	US1.1 (Agriculture)	-	Acker (arable land)
7	2.2	Permanent crops	veg01: AX_Landwirtschaft (Agriculture)	-	CS 2.1.3 (Other woody formations)	Gärtnerei, Obstplantagen (garden center and orchards) Weingarten (vine yards)

<i>Class</i>	<i>CLC Class</i>	<i>CLC Class name/OSMlanduse</i>	<i>digitales Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS) DE - Heidelberg</i>	<i>OCS-GE LU – FR Toulouse</i>	<i>OCS-GE LC – FR - Toulouse</i>	<i>Realnutzungskartierung 2018 Wien – AU- Vienna</i>
8	2.3	Pastures	veg01: AX_Landwirtschaft (Agriculture)	-	CS 2.2.1 (Herbaceous vegetation)	Wiese (meadows)
9	3.0	Forest and seminatural areas*	veg02: AX_Wald (Forest)	-	-	-
10	3.1	Forests	veg02: AX_Wald (Forest)	US1.5 (Other primary production); US1.2 (Forestry)	CS 2.1.1.1 (Hardwood forest); CS 2.1.1.3 (Mixed forest)	Wald (forest)
11	3.2	Shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations	veg02: AX_Wald (Forest)	US1.5 (Other primary production)	CS 2.1.2 (Shrubs); CS 2.2.2 (Other non-woody formations)	-
12	3.3	Open spaces with little or no vegetation	-	US1.5 (Other primary production)	CS 1.2.1 (Bare soil); CS 1.2.3 (Snow and ice)	-
13	5.0 (4.1, 4.2)	Water bodies Inland wetlands and	gew01: AX_Fliessgewaesser (rivers and streams)	US4.1.4 (Water transport); US1.4 (Aquaculture and fishing)	CS 1.2.2 (Water)	Gewässer inkl. Bachbett (rivers and streams)

4.2 OSMLanduse.org

The OSMLanduse product is a LULC map developed by Schultz et al. (2017) based on OSM and is available as a web map service (WMS) at www.osmlanduse.org. For this benchmark comparison, we modified the OSMLanduse product further by combining OSMLanduse CLC conversions created by Fonte et al. (2017) and the data created by Schultz et al. (2017) while refraining from any additional use of remote sensing data. As a result, OSMLanduse maps contained small areas with data gaps (as no gap filling was performed using remote sensing), but this was usually less than 5% for the study sites.

Table 4. Nomenclature of OSMLanduse.org and the tag-based legend harmonization towards CLC, modified (merged class 2.4 into 2.1, class 3.0 into class 3.1 and classes 4.1, 4.2 into 5.0) from Schultz et al. (2017)

<i>Class</i>	<i>CLC Class</i>	<i>CLC Class Name</i>	<i>Corresponding OSM tag for land use key</i>
1	1.1	Urban fabric	Residential
2	1.2	Industrial, commercial and transport units	industrial, commercial, retail, harbour, port, railway, lock, marina
3	1.3	Mine, dump and construction sites	quarry, construction, landfill, brownfield
4	1.4	Artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas	stadium, recreation ground, golf course, sports center, common, allotments, playground, pitch, village green, cemetery, park, zoo, track, garden
5	2.0	Agricultural areas	allotments, grass, greenhouse-horticulture, meadow
6	2.1	Arable land	greenhouse horticulture, greenhouse, farmland, farm, farmyard
7	2.2	Permanent crops	vineyard, orchard
8	2.3	Pastures	meadow
9	3.1	Forests	forest, wood
10	3.2	Shrub and/or herbaceous vegetation associations	grass, greenfield, scrub, heath, grassland
11	3.3	Open spaces with little or no vegetation	fell, sand, scree, beach, mud, glacier, rock, cliff
12	5.0	Water bodies (Inland wetlands, coastal wetlands)	march, wetland, salt pond, tidal, water, riverbank, reservoir, basin, dock, canal, pond

The methodology to produce the benchmark maps followed two steps. First, all OSM objects matching the key “land use” and a set of values was linked to a CLC class. The combination of key value pairs and the corresponding CLC class is shown in Table 4. Second, whenever gaps were presented or OSM objects of a finer resolution were available, we filled existing gaps using an automatic approach of OSM object matches

and Urban Atlas (UA) (Barranco et al., 2014) and Globeland 30 (GL30)⁹. A stepwise procedure was developed as follows:

- 1) A set of OSM keys and values that could be associated with each class of interest in the target LULC map are first selected.
- 2) Linear features of interest, such as roads, are then converted to area features. This step is accomplished using either predefined values that depend on the type of feature or using a procedure to compute the distance to the closest features, which defines the limits of the resulting area feature, such as the presence of buildings.
- 3) Polygons corresponding to the same class are merged.
- 4) Inconsistencies are removed; these can result from overlapping polygons corresponding to different non-compatible classes, where a list of class priorities is used based on their relative importance, size and the most common spatial and topological relations.

The full methodology is described in Fonte et al. (2017). The OSM object conversion method described in that paper was generally sufficient to convert OSM into land use with some minor technical modifications that are outside the scope of this report. The initial demonstration of the method was performed on the city of Heidelberg as described in Schultz et al. (2017). The overall accuracy was 87%, which outperformed the CLC product from 2012. For more details about the method and the results, the reader should refer to Schultz et al. (2017).

4.3 Case studies

This section provides detailed results for the benchmarking of the OSMLanduse data for the three case study cities shown in Figure 21. Overall results showed that residential and commercial/industrial usage was found to be particularly confused when comparing national products and the OSM based product. These differences could be attributed to the legend harmonization process due to differences in mixed classes. Both the Austrian and French national products allow a set of mixed classes regarding residential and commercial land use while the OSMLanduse map provides more rigorous class distinctions between residential and commercial/industrial. As a result, this created confusion particularly between urban and industrial classes. Thematic agreement of OSMLanduse and CLC was generally higher than with the converted national products. Like OSMLanduse, CLC avoids mixed classes. Second, the most common confusion was found between artificial vegetated green areas, agriculture and herbaceous surfaces.

The level of spatial detail of the maps varied greatly. The German national product was only available in parts for Heidelberg. In contrast, the Austrian national product was available open source for the entire area of interest and in great spatial detail. Similarly, the French national product was available in great spatial detail. Legal issues for data usage and data availability varied by country, and therefore, affected the comparison.

Differences between the mapping units used in each dataset were not compared as they define the sensitivity of the comparison. Additionally, we did not compare the differences in accuracy between the maps, although

⁹ http://www.globallandcover.com/home_en.html

this will be subject of a future research paper. Detailed results and a description of the data used for each of the three benchmarking case studies can be found in the following sections.

4.3.1 Case study: Germany (Heidelberg)

4.3.1.1 Digitales Landschaftsmodell (ATKIS) DE – data description

Each state in Germany has its own land use information system reflecting their respective priorities; detail and content vary in terms of extent, spatial detail and thematic depth. The state of Baden-Württemberg (BaWü), in which Heidelberg is located, does not offer one coherent land use map free of charge but refers to CORINE products frequently. Existing mapping products of the respective BaWü ministry¹⁰ are highly specialised, focusing on aspects such as biospheres, air quality, or energy sites.

At a federal level, the land cover products for Germany 2009, 2012, 2015 and 2018 (Digitales Landbedeckungsmodell für Deutschland) exist but are not available free of charge and are only available for specific state institutions (<https://gdz.bkg.bund.de/>). However, it is similar to the existing CORINE products in that it uses a similar legend and, in many parts, agrees with CORINE. However, it was produced using Rapideye¹¹ data and is available at a resolution of approximately 5m whereas the CLC2018 data was produced using Landsat-8 and Sentinel-2 satellite imagery (Büttner et al., 2017). Given the increased importance of EU-based decision making, CORINE products are increasingly becoming the new standard in Germany.

4.3.1.2 ATKIS and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 22 shows the comparison between ATKIS 2018 and OSMLanduse 2018 for Heidelberg. The top row figures show the original products while the bottom row figures show the difference between the two products, where the grey area indicates agreement. The disagreement between the two maps is shown from the perspective of both products as undertaken in previous work (Schultz et al., 2017). As shown, the majority of both difference maps are grey (showing agreement). The spatial areas of disagreement are similar for both difference maps, but the nature of the disagreement differs. For example, the majority of disagreement in the ATKIS map is shown in red (class 1.1 - urban fabric), indicating that the ATKIS mapping showed a larger area of urban fabric than in the OSMLanduse data for the case study area (see ATKIS and OSMLanduse sum totals in Table 5 for confirmation). In comparison, the OSMLanduse difference map shows a broader range of land use class differences. The majority of differences are shown in pink (class 1.2 - Industrial, commercial and transport units), but there are also significant areas shown in yellow (agricultural land) and green (forests). Despite this, it is clear that the majority of the confusion between the two datasets is between classes 1.1 and 1.2.

¹⁰ <https://udo.lubw.baden-wuerttemberg.de/public/>

¹¹ <https://directory.eoportal.org/web/eoportal/satellite-missions/r/rapideye>

Figure 22: Heidelberg comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and ATKIS 2018. The top row shows the original products and the bottom row shows the difference where grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the ATKIS difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for agricultural land (yellow) and forests (green)

Table 5 illustrates the confusion matrix between OSMLanduse and ATKIS classifications for the Heidelberg case study area. The cells in green represent the agreement between the two classifications (following the harmonization from Table 3) while the other cells represent the confusion. Cells highlighted in orange

represent significant classification errors. The NA ATKIS column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse that do not have homogeneous classes in the ATKIS data. The NA OSM row represents the percentage of the total area from ATKIS data that do not have homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. From these two columns, we can see that 32.72% of the total area from OSMLanduse in Heidelberg has no correspondence in the ATKIS data and 5.53% of the total area from ATKIS has no correspondence in OSMLanduse.

Table 5: Heidelberg confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show ATKIS (Overall agreement – 57.7%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		ATKIS						Sum OSMLanduse
		1.1	1.2	2.0	3.0	5.0	NA ATKIS	
OSMLanduse	1.1	9.27	0.17	0.00	0.15	0.03	0.90	10.52
	1.2	7.48	3.50	0.03	0.51	0.08	3.44	15.05
	2.0	0.51	0.05	0.57	0.07	0.05	21.02	22.27
	3.0	1.46	0.03	0.03	39.77	0.11	3.26	44.66
	5.0	0.08	0.00	0.00	0.02	1.16	0.70	1.96
	NA OSM	1.40	0.46	0.06	0.16	0.05	3.41	5.53
sum ATKIS		20.20	4.21	0.69	40.69	1.48	32.72	

In addition to the class 1.1- Urban fabric, other classes have good agreement with the ATKIS LULC map, for example:

- Class 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation (3.5% out of 4.21% of the total area of the ATKIS dataset).
- Class 3.0-Forest and Semi-natural areas (39.77% out of 40.69% of the total area in the ATKIS dataset shows agreement).

We can, however, notice a confusion between classes 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation and 1.1 - Urban fabric (7.48%). Thus, for the Heidelberg case, we can conclude that the agreement between the two classifications is good. However, the incomplete data (areas not having correspondence in ATKIS or OSMLanduse data) is relevant.

4.3.1.3 CORINE Land Cover (CLC) and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 23 shows the comparison between CLC 2018 and OSMLanduse 2018 for Heidelberg. The top row figures show the original products while bottom row figures show the difference between the two products, where grey areas indicate agreement. It can be observed that the forest and hydrographic classes have a good agreement whereas the classes 1.1-Urban fabric, 1.2- Industrial, commercial and transport units, 2.0-Agricultural areas, and 2.1-Arable land show disagreements.

Figure 23: Heidelberg comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC2018. Top row shows original products, the bottom row shows differences while the grey area shows agreement. The largest mismatches are shown in yellow (arable land) for the CLC data and white (agricultural areas) for similar areas of the OSMLanduse data

Table 6 represents the confusion matrix between CLC and OSMLanduse classes. The green cells represent the agreement between the two classifications while the other cells represent the confusion. Cells highlighted in orange represent significant classification errors. The NA CLC column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the CLC data. The NA OSM row represents

the percentage of the total area from CLC data that do not have homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. All OSMLanduse mapped areas found correspondences in the CLC product (see column NA CLC) while 4.10% of the total area mapped in the CLC was not mapped in the OSMLanduse data (see column sum OSMLanduse for NA OSM row).

We can observe that there is generally a good agreement for class 1.1-Urban fabric, while 2.1-Arable land show disagreements. For the classes 2.2-Permanent crops, 3.1- Forests, and 5.0- Water bodies Inland wetlands, more than half of the total area from Heidelberg belongs to the same classes in both the OSMLanduse and CLC data. Especially for the class 3.1- Forests, the agreement is very high (e.g., 41.26 % out of 43.61% of the total CLC surface area).

High confusion is evident between the classes 1.2 and 1.1 (6.24 % of the total surface of Heidelberg area is classified as class 1.2 in OSMLanduse data and 1.1 in CLC) and the classes 2.0 and 2.1 (18.29 % of the total area of Heidelberg is classified in class 2.0 in OSMLanduse data and 2.1 in CLC). Since class 2.1 (arable crops) is effectively a subclass of agricultural land (2.0), this confusion is not surprising. The misclassification of urban fabric (1.1) and industrial/commercial land (1.2) is also likely to be due to similarities between the two land use types, i.e., commercial/industrial land use is often a part of the urban fabric.

Table 6: Heidelberg confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show CLC 2018 (overall agreement is 58.6%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		CLC									Sum
		1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.1	2.2	3.1	5.0	NA CLC	Osmlanduse
OSMLanduse	1.1	9.31	0.43	0.00	0.02	0.21	0.08	0.45	0.03	0.00	10.52
	1.2	6.24	5.44	0.09	0.79	1.47	0.13	0.72	0.17	0.00	15.05
	1.3	0.14	0.22	0.13	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.51
	1.4	0.49	0.08	0.00	0.22	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.93
	2.0	0.46	0.11	0.04	0.25	18.29	2.06	0.15	0.00	0.00	21.36
	2.1	0.10	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.27
	2.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.24	0.40	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.64
	3.1	0.28	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.20	0.21	41.26	0.10	0.00	42.13
	3.2	0.11	0.23	0.05	0.01	1.16	0.29	0.54	0.07	0.00	2.45
	3.3	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.07
	5.0	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.05	0.03	0.00	0.15	1.71	0.00	1.96
NA OSM	0.92	0.67	0.07	0.23	1.65	0.23	0.20	0.13	0.00	4.10	
sum CLC		18.07	7.22	0.37	1.64	23.46	3.40	43.61	2.23		

4.3.2 Case study: France (Toulouse)

4.3.2.1 OCS-GE data description

OCS-GE is LULC data produced by IGN (French National Mapping Agency). It relies on a common nomenclature of distinct LU and LC classes, based on the CNIG (French National Committee of Geographic Information) specifications and is INSPIRE-compliant (INSPIRE, 2013). The territory is divided into non-overlapping polygons, where each polygon feature is described by both LU and LC. The mapping is then made

with respect to the data specifications (IGN, 2015) including the nomenclature, rules, and thresholds of assignment. The mapping process is carried out in three steps. First, an initial outline of LULC land parcels is generated from the network of main roads and railways. These cover the whole country and so provide a valid regional structure for the landscape that is relatively long lasting and ensures the geometric consistency of the data over time. Secondly, polygons with distinct LU and LC values are computed using a semi-automated process by integrating several authoritative databases (e.g., topographic layers such as buildings, the secondary road network, etc., a forest layer, and a cadastral layer). Finally, a manual step based on photo-interpretation is undertaken to correct errors and fill in the gaps in terms of LU and LC values. Three hierarchical levels are proposed for LC classes and four hierarchical levels for LU classes (IGN, 2015). In total, the proposed nomenclature contains 17 LU classes and 14 LC classes (see Table 3). However, not every combination between LU and LC classes, i.e., 17×14 , is possible as some LC values are only applicable to specific LU values and vice-versa. For example, LC class 1.1.1.1 (built up areas) cannot be applied to LU class 1.1 (agriculture).

4.3.2.2 OCS-GE and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 24 shows the comparison between OCS-GE land cover 2016 and OSMLanduse 2018 for the Toulouse case. As in the previous case study, the top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference between the two products and grey areas indicate agreement. It can be observed that the maps showing the difference are very fragmented, demonstrating the heterogeneity between the two products.

The confusion matrix between the translated OCS-GE land cover classes and original OSMLanduse classes (CLC compliant) is shown in Table 7. The NA OCS column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the OCS-GE LC. Similarly, the NA OSM row represents the percentage of the total area from OCS-GE LC that does not have homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. From these two columns, we can see that there is no area in the OSMLanduse not having homogeneous classes in the OCS-GE LC while there are some areas in OCS-GE LC without corresponding classes in OSMLanduse (e.g., the class 23- Pastures is the class with less correspondence in OSMLanduse. In total, 6.48% of the area is classified as pastures in OCS-GE and not classified in OSMLanduse).

Figure 24. Toulouse comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and OCS-GE land cover 2016. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the OCS-GE difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for urban fabric (red) and forests (green)

Agreement on class 5.0 (water) is good (2.21%) with the citizen derived OSM product showing a total area of 2.48% while the authoritative mapping shows 2.56%. However, significant errors can be seen for some of the LULC classes, namely:

- The class 1.1- Urban fabric (8.9% of the total area from Toulouse is classified in the class 1.1-Urban fabric in OSMLanduse) and belongs to 2.3- Pastures in OCS-GE LC).

- The class 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation (11.3% of the total area from Toulouse is classified in the class 1.2- Industrial, Commercial and Transportation in OSMLanduse and belongs to 11-Urban fabric in OCS-GE LC).
- 10.3% of the of the total area from Toulouse is classified in the class 12 in OSMLanduse and belongs to 23- Pastures in OCS-GE LC.

The confusion between the 1.1 and 1.2 classes can be partially explained by the n: m correspondence links between the nomenclature, but the confusion between the classes 1.1 and 1.2 (in OSMLanduse) and 23 (pastures) in OCS-GE LC is, however, surprising. A potential reason for this mismatch could be due to the differences between mapping units where built up areas (OSMLanduse classes 1.1 and 1.2) were adjacent to pastures (OCS-GE LC class 23) leading to confusion when comparing datasets.

Table 7. Toulouse confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show OCS-GE LC classes 2016 (overall agreement = 36.1%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		OCS-GE LC classes									Sum
		11	12	13	22	23	31	32	50 NA OCS		
OSMLanduse classes	1.1	13.46	2.63	0.42	0.00	8.90	2.03	0.04	0.13	0.00	27.61
	1.2	11.31	18.47	1.36	0.00	10.31	1.85	0.21	0.05	0.00	43.56
	1.3	0.03	0.04	0.10	0.00	0.20	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.38
	1.4	0.08	0.30	0.08	0.00	2.45	1.02	0.03	0.03	0.00	3.99
	2.0	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.14	3.50	0.20	0.12	0.00	0.00	4.04
	2.1	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.51	0.10	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.67
	2.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3.1	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.40	1.71	0.08	0.07	0.00	2.29
	3.2	0.01	0.08	0.06	0.00	2.93	0.16	0.11	0.00	0.00	3.35
	5.0	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.07	0.17	0.00	2.21	0.00	2.48
	NA OSM	0.92	2.17	0.48	0.01	6.48	1.31	0.20	0.06	0.00	11.63
sum OCS-GE LC		25.85	23.76	2.56	0.15	35.76	8.55	0.82	2.56	0.00	

Table 8 represents the confusion matrix between the translated OCS-GE LU and original OSMLanduse classes. Similar to OCS-GE LC, the NA OCS column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the OCS-GE LU. The NA OSM row represents the percentage of the total area from the OCS-GE LU that does not have homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. We can observe that for LU classes, there are areas mapped in OSMLanduse without homogeneous classes in the OCS-GE LU (see column NA OCS). This is unsurprising because the OCS-GE LU is focused only on land use classes whereas OSMLanduse is a mix between LU and LC classes.

Concerning agreement, once again the class 5.0-Water bodies inland has the highest agreement with respect to the total area classified in 5.0 in OCS-GE LU. It is followed by the class 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation where half of the total area belongs to the same class in both datasets. We can also observe a high disagreement (i.e., 26.41%) between the classes 1.1 - Urban fabric and 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation. Here the disagreement may come from the fact that the land use and land cover classes are mixed in OSMLanduse.

Table 8. Toulouse confusion matrix where rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 and columns show OCS-GE LU classes 2016 (Overall agreement = 44.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		OCS-GE LU classes							Sum Osmlanduse
		1.0	1.2	1.3	2.1	3.1	5.0	NA OCS	
Osmlanduse	1.1	0.14	26.41	0.00	0.50	0.15	0.02	0.37	27.61
	1.2	0.39	41.35	0.00	0.63	0.29	0.01	0.89	43.56
	1.3	0.11	0.12	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.38
	1.4	0.00	2.86	0.00	0.39	0.43	0.00	0.31	3.99
	2.0	0.01	0.34	0.00	3.36	0.14	0.00	0.17	4.04
	2.1	0.00	0.33	0.00	0.21	0.02	0.00	0.11	0.67
	2.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3.1	0.01	0.39	0.00	0.25	1.37	0.00	0.27	2.29
	3.2	0.07	2.27	0.00	0.56	0.15	0.00	0.30	3.35
	5.0	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.01	0.08	0.24	1.92	2.48
NA OSM	0.14	8.75	0.01	1.47	0.24	0.02	1.00	11.63	
sum OCS-GE LU		0.88	83.06	0.02	7.39	2.88	0.30	5.49	

Overall, for the Toulouse case, the comparison results are good for some OSMLanduse classes, e.g., 5.0. However, some confusion exists for non-urban classes and particularly between the two “urban classes” (classes 1.1 and 1.2). In our opinion, this is due to significant differences between the two LULC classification systems used and the fact that in the OSMLanduse product, the land use and land cover are mixed. For example, the OCS-GE land use classification does not distinguish between residential and industrial/commercial land (see Table 3) and the land cover classification only includes a single “built-up area” class that includes both types of land use (Table 3). This explains the confusion between OSMLanduse classes 1.1 and 1.2. When the results for these LULC types are combined, the overall accuracy for these combined classes is much greater, i.e., 92.5% (45.87/49.61) for the land cover comparison and 81.4% (68.29/83.94) for the land use data.

4.3.2.3 CORINE Land Cover (CLC) and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 25 shows the comparison between CORINE 2018 and OSMLanduse 2018 for the Toulouse case. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference between the two products and grey areas indicate agreement, as described in more detail in the previous case study for Heidelberg. Comparing with Figure 24 (national product - OCS-GE 2018), we can observe that the differences maps are less fragmented for CORINE, which is because the two products have similar nomenclatures.

Figure 25. Toulouse comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC2018. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and grey areas indicate agreement. The red areas in the CLC difference map show that the majority of the mismatches relate to urban fabric land classes with industrial/commercial (pink) and arable land (yellow) also present. In the OSMLanduse difference map, the majority of differences are shown in pink (Industrial, commercial and transport) with some additional mismatches for urban fabric (red) and forests (green)

Table 9 represents the confusion matrix between CLC and OSMLanduse classes for the Toulouse case. The NA CLC column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the CLC data. The NA OSM row represents the percentage of the total area from CLC data that does not have homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. We can observe that all OSMLanduse mapped areas found correspondences in the CLC product (see column NA CLC) and 11.63% of the total area are mapped in CLC but not mapped in OSMLanduse data. For the LU classes, there are areas mapped in

OSMlanduse without homogeneous classes in the CLC (see column NA CLC). This is because CLC is focused only on land cover classes whereas OSMlanduse is a mix between LU and LC classes.

Table 9. Toulouse confusion matrix - rows show area percentages OSMlanduse 2018 and columns show CLC2018 (overall agreement = 46.5%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		CLC									Sum
		1.1	1.2	1.4	2.1	2.2	3.1	3.2	5.0	NA CLC	OsmLanduse
OSMlanduse	1.1	24.08	1.93	0.54	0.64	0.00	0.17	0.08	0.17	0.00	27.61
	1.2	22.32	18.14	1.62	0.93	0.03	0.33	0.09	0.10	0.00	43.56
	1.3	0.06	0.32	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.38
	1.4	1.50	0.27	1.54	0.32	0.00	0.16	0.18	0.02	0.00	3.99
	2.0	0.35	0.29	0.01	3.03	0.13	0.05	0.14	0.04	0.00	4.04
	2.1	0.13	0.22	0.01	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.00	0.67
	2.2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
	3.1	0.21	0.21	0.32	0.49	0.00	0.86	0.16	0.04	0.00	2.29
	3.2	0.14	2.16	0.02	0.79	0.00	0.04	0.19	0.00	0.00	3.35
	5.0	0.28	0.21	0.17	0.11	0.00	0.09	0.05	1.56	0.00	2.48
	NA OSM	4.91	4.18	0.49	1.69	0.05	0.14	0.06	0.11	0.00	11.63
sum CLC		53.97	27.94	4.74	8.17	0.21	1.85	1.10	2.04	0.00	

Concerning the agreement, the higher agreement is obtained for the classes 1.1-Urban fabric class, 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation, and 5.0-Water bodies Inland and the biggest confusion is between 1.1-Urban fabric and 1.2 - Industrial, Commercial and Transportation (i.e., 22.32%).

Globally, the agreement between the two classifications for the Toulouse pilot is quite weak. This is mainly due to the significant confusion between Urban Fabric (1.1) and Industrial/commercial (1.2) LULC classes.

4.3.3 Case study: Austria (Vienna)

4.3.3.1 Realnutzung – data description

The Austrian Realnutzung has been available since 2007 and is updated at least biannually. It is an exclusive product for the city of Vienna. The latest version is available for the year 2018 and for this comparison with OSMlanduse. This dataset depicts the actual land use of Vienna in a generalized form. The data are based on an interpretation of aerial photography supplemented by additional ancillary data¹². There are 32 usage categories from the areas of living, green spaces, traffic, etc. The usage categories are hierarchically divided into 3 levels. Data quality and accuracy are verified using local knowledge from MA 18 and MA 21 (administrative units of the municipality). The building blocks of the spatial reference system of Vienna

¹² See the following link (in German) for more detailed information on the Realnutzung dataset - <https://www.wien.gv.at/stadtentwicklung/grundlagen/stadtforschung/siedlungsentwicklung/realnutzungskartierung/>

represent the geometric basis. The data are easily accessible through <https://www.data.gv.at/katalog/dataset/2f5baa1f-208c-42c2-8d04-9ea74aa1b229>, which follows transparent open data principles. Translation towards CLC was directly provide by the LandSense partner Umweltbundesamt (UBA) in Vienna (by Gebhard Banko).

4.3.3.2 Realnutzung and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 26. Vienna comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and Realnutzung. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas show agreement. The Realnutzung difference map indicates that the majority of the mismatches relate to industrial/commercial (pink), urban fabric (red), arable land (yellow) and forest (green) land classes. The

OSMlanduse difference map shows similar class differences except that forests and arable land are replaced by agricultural areas (white)

Figure 26 shows the comparison between Realnutzung and OSMlanduse 2018 for the Vienna case study. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference between the two products and the grey areas show agreement. It can be observed that, as for Toulouse case, the maps illustrating the difference are very fragmented, showing the heterogeneity between the two products.

Table 10 shows the confusion matrix between the translated Realnutzung product and the original OSMlanduse classes (CLC compliant). The NA Realnutzung column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMlanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the Realnutzung product, whereas the NA OSM row represents the percentage of the total area from the Realnutzung product that does not have homogeneous classes in the OSMlanduse. From these two columns, we can see that there is no area in the OSMlanduse that does not have homogeneous classes in the Realnutzung product, while there are a few areas in the Realnutzung product without corresponding classing in OSMlanduse.

Concerning the agreement, it is not very high, with an overall accuracy just below 50% (49.3%). For the class 5.0-Water bodies Inland, 3.75 % of 4.64 % of the total area in Vienna is classified in the class 5.0 in both OSMlanduse and Realnutzung. For classes such as 1.1-Urban Fabric, 1.2- Industrial, commercial and transport units, and 3.1-Forests, half of the total area is classified in the same classes in both the Realnutzung product and OSMlanduse. As with the previous case studies, confusion is evident for the classes 1.1-Urban Fabric and 1.2- Industrial, commercial and transport units (see orange cells in Table 10).

Table 10. Vienna confusion matrix -rows show area percentages of OSMlanduse 2018, columns show Realnutzung (overall agreement = 49.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		Realnutzung (RNZ) product										Sum Osmlanduse
		1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	5.0	NA RNZ	
OSMlanduse	1.1	13.71	5.24	0.03	0.42	0.04	0.13	0.12	0.09	0.02	0.00	19.80
	1.2	5.79	14.75	0.33	2.40	0.19	0.19	0.37	0.42	0.11	0.00	24.54
	1.3	0.15	0.21	0.64	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.00	1.08
	1.4	2.72	1.29	0.04	2.95	0.05	0.09	0.88	1.48	0.15	0.00	9.64
	2.0	2.20	0.77	0.05	0.03	8.16	0.44	0.43	4.66	0.03	0.00	16.77
	2.1	0.08	0.13	0.02	0.06	0.62	0.89	0.10	0.06	0.01	0.00	1.96
	2.2	0.07	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.10	1.51	0.04	0.03	0.00	0.00	1.89
	2.3	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.16	0.11	0.02	0.00	0.37
	3.1	0.17	0.65	0.01	0.13	0.09	0.04	0.69	11.21	0.43	0.00	13.43
	3.2	0.14	0.26	0.01	0.17	0.28	0.09	1.69	0.45	0.07	0.00	3.16
	3.3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.02
	5.0	0.02	0.05	0.00	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.12	0.10	3.75	0.00	4.11
	NA OSM	0.45	0.79	0.07	0.22	0.78	0.26	0.48	0.13	0.05	0.00	3.23
Sum RNZ		25.51	24.32	1.21	6.47	10.36	3.65	5.10	18.76	4.64	0.00	

4.3.3.3 CORINE Land Cover and OSMLanduse Comparison

Figure 27 shows the comparison between CLC 2018 and OSMLanduse 2018 for Vienna case. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference between the two products and the grey areas indicate agreement. Surprisingly, it can be observed that, as for Toulouse case, that the maps illustrating the difference are very fragmented showing the heterogeneity between the two products.

Figure 27. Vienna comparison of OSMLanduse 2018 and CLC. The top row shows the original products, the bottom row shows the difference and the grey areas indicate agreement. The CLC difference map [bottom left] shows a diverse set of mismatched LULC

classes as does the difference map for OSMLanduse [bottom right]. Urban fabric (red) is mismatched with Industrial/Commercial (pink) and forests (green) and arable land (yellow) are mismatched with the more general agricultural areas (white) in the LULC classification.

Table 11 represents the confusion matrix between the CLC product and original OSMLanduse classes. As with the previous case studies, the NA CLC column represents the percentage of the total area from OSMLanduse not having homogeneous classes in the CLC product, whereas NA OSM line represents the percentage of the total area from CLC data not having homogeneous classes in the OSMLanduse. From these two columns, we can see that there is no area in the OSMLanduse not having homogeneous classes in the CLC product and there are some few areas in CLC product without corresponding classing in OSMLanduse.

Agreement between the two datasets is even lower than the previous case with overall accuracy of around 30% (31.3%) for the class 5.0-Water bodies Inland 2.89 % among 3.46 % of the total area in Vienna belongs to class 5.0 in both OSMLanduse and CLC. For classes such as 1.2- Industrial, commercial and transport units, and 1.4- Artificial non-agricultural vegetated areas, half of the total area is classified in the same classes in both the CLC product and OSMLanduse. For this comparison, we can notice high confusion for 1.2- Industrial, commercial and transport units (14.75% is confused with 1.1), 2.0- Agricultural areas (8.62% from the total area is confused to 2.1- Arable land) and 3.1-Forests (11.11% of the total area is confused to 2.3- Pastures).

Table 11. Vienna confusion matrix - rows show area percentages of OSMLanduse 2018 area and columns show CLC (overall agreement = 31.3%). Green highlighted cells show agreement between the two datasets and cells highlighted in orange represent cases of substantial disagreement

		CLC											Sum Osmlanduse
		1.1	1.2	1.3	1.4	2.1	2.2	2.3	3.1	5.0	NA CLC		
OSMLanduse	1.1	18.75	0.61	0.15	0.06	0.13	0.03	0.06	0.00	0.01	0.00	19.80	
	1.2	14.75	6.66	1.54	0.48	0.64	0.04	0.32	0.00	0.11	0.00	24.54	
	1.3	0.27	0.35	0.36	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.08	
	1.4	4.85	0.22	3.62	0.48	0.14	0.00	0.16	0.00	0.17	0.00	9.64	
	2.0	2.96	0.18	0.20	0.08	8.62	0.08	4.62	0.01	0.01	0.00	16.77	
	2.1	0.51	0.80	0.03	0.01	0.54	0.01	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.96	
	2.2	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.25	1.35	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.89	
	2.3	0.05	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.01	0.17	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.37	
	3.1	0.80	0.13	0.42	0.00	0.82	0.03	11.11	0.05	0.06	0.00	13.43	
	3.2	0.76	0.15	0.08	0.01	1.28	0.02	0.76	0.07	0.03	0.00	3.16	
	3.3	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.02	
	5.0	0.39	0.09	0.22	0.02	0.07	0.00	0.31	0.04	2.98	0.00	4.11	
NA OSM	1.22	0.53	0.12	0.04	1.08	0.12	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.00	3.23		
Sum CLC		45.58	9.75	6.74	1.19	13.73	1.70	17.67	0.18	3.46	0.00		

4.4 Citizen-contributed data and cost reductions

A potential workflow for integrating VGI data in NMA authoritative mapping data was outlined in deliverable 5.5 (Liu et al., 2020). It had been proposed to update portions of the OCS-GE dataset covering the Toulouse case study area using citizen-contributed data (i.e., data collected through the LandSense campaigns for the Toulouse pilot). To evaluate the quality of the automated process proposed in deliverable 5.5, our results will

first be compared with the traditional OCS-GE 2019 product, which covered the same period as the LandSense Toulouse pilot study. Then, in a second step, the costs for producing both OCS-GE (traditional method versus integrating citizen-contributed data) will be estimated in order to evaluate any cost reductions that could be achieved by using citizen-contributed data relative to using traditional authoritative mapping techniques.

The latest version of the OCS-GE 2019 LULC map created using traditional mapping techniques was to be published early in 2020. Unfortunately, the release of the OCS-GE 2019 has been delayed due to the COVID-19 pandemic and will now not be released until the end of 2020, ruling out its inclusion within this deliverable. However, this important work element is still to be performed when the OCS-GE 2019 dataset becomes available, and the results will be the subject of a future scientific publication.

5 Conclusions

This work brings together results and lessons learnt from the previous six deliverables (D5.1 – D5.6) created as part of the Quality Assurance work package of the LandSense project. The challenges encountered in the development of robust data models for a diverse set of citizen science campaigns were highlighted in section 2. It was found that a compromise should be reached between maintaining data protocols and schemas rigidly (to simplify and streamline QA processes) whilst still allowing flexibility for each campaign to identify a data model that fits their subject area and requirements. Some common data elements (e.g., GPS accuracy) and formats (e.g., geojson) are necessary to enable effective QA processes to be performed, but these were defined in a consensual manner to encourage buy-in from each pilot study.

Examples of good practice identified throughout the project were outlined for each QA check in section 3 and are summarised in Table 12. Note that, as stated in the introduction, these are for guidance and information and should not be treated as the only or “best” solution. The specific requirements and context of a LULC-based VGI exercise will be a key driver in the applicability and utility of the various good practices shown. As with the discussion of data protocols, the application of many of the practices shown is a compromise between maximising data quality whilst maintaining important features such as contributor engagement. For example, the addition of image resolution checks for photos is only applicable where older mobile devices may be used in image collection. The need to introduce more complex methods for assessing positional accuracy and offset is highly relevant where users are tasked with assessing small features (such as in the urban pilot studies: MijnPark.NL and City.Oases), but it is of lower importance when features are large and easier to observe (e.g., agricultural pilots such as CropSupport).

Elements of the work carried out in the pilot studies were assessed against authoritative maps (section 4) and show the potential of VGI as an effective and accurate method for monitoring LULC. Where errors were identified between VGI and authoritative datasets, a large proportion can be assigned to issues relating to differences between mapping units between the products and the translation issues between the OSMIanduse LULC classification system and the NMA/CLC system of LULC classification. The final point shown in Table 12, LULC class harmonization, was found to be of high importance, as demonstrated by the benchmarking work described in section 4. Where possible, designers of citizen observatory projects making LULC observations should endeavour to align their classification system with national standards as closely as possible. Where divergence exists, efforts should be made to identify the closest LULC match to national standards and include this information in their data model. The recent EU-funded EAGLE project (Arnold et al., 2013) provides detailed information related to the issues of harmonizing LULC classification systems and how this can increase the value of LULC projects.

Further work will continue and extend the benchmarking processes described here and form the basis of a future LandSense publication. This will potentially include alternate methods for performing the conversion between different mapping units and the inclusion of more detail into the translation of VGI to national LULC classification systems.

Table 12: Good practice summary table

QA check	Good practice	Description
	Snapping and editing tools	Addition of polygon editing tools to apps to allow users to edit polygons at the time of data collection.
	Overlap flagging	Allow users to choose to flag existing polygons as being inaccurate when overlaps occur to remove issue where new polygons cannot be added if they overlap existing (potentially erroneous) polygons.
Image Processing	Integrate quality and privacy checking ¹	Improve privacy check accuracy where photo quality is poor by performing privacy check on improved version of image.
	Image resolution check	Addition of image resolution (and potential automatic upscaling) checks may be a useful QA tool where image quality is critical and camera technology used to collect images is poor.
Photo Illumination checking	Add threshold for extreme brightness	Add functionality to set a maximum brightness threshold to identify images where extreme brightness leads to reduction in photo quality and detail.
	Automatic brightening ¹³	Use of standard brightening algorithms to increase overall image brightness. Unlikely to work on extremely dark images. Image contrast may need to be increased in order to maintain image detail.
Photo blur check	Automatic sharpening ¹	Sharpening algorithms have been shown to be able to reduce image blur where blurriness is not excessive. Unlikely to improve quality of extremely blurred images.
Photo privacy check	Use of 3 rd party LPDS ¹⁴ and manual verification checks	Where 100% accuracy is critical, it may be necessary to consider using 3 rd party services and/or visual verification checks to ensure that all privacy features have been successfully identified and obscured.
	Intelligent detection threshold definition	Variable privacy detection thresholds applied based on the likelihood of privacy features being present in data collected. Higher (less chance of detection) thresholds to reduce commission errors where privacy features not likely to occur. Lower (stricter) thresholds where probability of privacy features is higher (e.g., urban scenes).

¹³ The reader should note that modifications to a user's images would need to be allowed under the licensing arrangements for the data collection exercise before these actions could be carried out

¹⁴ LPDS = License Plate Detection Service

QA check	Good practice	Description
Positional accuracy and offset	Integrate accuracy into campaign design	When designing a campaign, the likely accuracy of user’s devices, based on GPS accuracy of device and obstructions to GPS signal at location, should be considered. Where high positional accuracy is required to make good observations, observation point should be chosen to avoid poor GPS accuracy.
	Location beacons at guided observation points	For guided campaigns, infrastructure (e.g., QR code or Bluetooth beacon) could be added to observation point to ensure that contributors are at the correct location.
	Variable offset definition	Offset threshold should be directly related to observation requirements for each point of interest (POI). Smaller POIs might require a contributor to be within 5-10m to make observations. Larger POIs may only require an offset of 20-30m.
Contributor Agreement Categorical Accuracy	LULC classification harmonization with domain standards	LULC categories should be defined in accordance with national classification standards as far as is possible. Divergence reduces the ability to benchmark and the potential value of the data. Where strict alignment is not possible, care should be taken to define new LULC categories in a way that simplifies mapping to national LULC classification systems.

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